

Hemiolic Mode as Post-Hellenistic Development of the Chromatic System:

*The Ancient Greek Roots of Mediterranean Tonality
and Its Hemiolic Typology.*

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The Ancient Greek roots of Mediterranean Tonality and its Hemiolic Typology and their antithesis to Western tonality

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Introduction. The reasons for conceptualizing the Hemiolic musical mode

Virtually every music theory textbook, even the most basic, contains an entry on the so-called “harmonic minor” in a section dedicated to the explanation of a minor key. Usually, “harmonic minor” is explained as a modification of “natural minor” that occurs “naturally” via the inversion of a relative major key: e.g., C Major (C-D-E-F-G-A-B) becomes inverted into its relative key of A Minor (A-B-C-D-E-F-G) whenever the VI degree of a major key is adopted as a new tonic while keeping all pitch classes the same. “Harmonic” variety of a minor key raises its VII degree (“G” of the natural A minor turns into “G sharp”) to emphasize the harmonic contrast between the so-called "dominant" harmonic function that becomes major in a harmonic minor (E-G#-B as opposed to the minor dominant E-G-B of the natural minor), on the one hand, and the "tonic" harmony that remains minor, on the other hand.

Melodies, created in a minor key and harmonized with the chords based on such dominant harmonies (e.g., triads and 7-chords built on the V and the VII degrees), greatly benefit from the harmonic contrast between dominant and tonic functions. As a result of this harmonic enhancement that makes cadences more salient and thereby increases the salience of harmonic resolutions, melodies sustained in harmonic minor obtain a characteristic trait, easily recognizable by ear even by musically untrained listeners – an interval of the augmented second generated between the VI and the VII degrees (F-G#). This interval is

responsible for common association of the sound of melodies entirely restricted to "harmonic minor" with Jewish, Turkish and Persian music.

Indeed, musical modes that contain the same intervallic structure as Western "harmonic minor" (tone/semitone/tone/tone/semitone/tone-and-a-half) are exceedingly common for Jewish, Arabic, Turkish, Persian music cultures, as well as folk music of most Balkan countries. Obviously, the presence of the augmented second in music of all these cultures cannot be explained in the same way as Western "harmonic minor" for a simple reason that in all of them, except perhaps Jewish music, harmony does not carry any formative power. That is, these music cultures employ exclusively melodic expression, arranging it in monophonic and/or heterophonic textures, only recently introducing some limited use of chords and basic harmonization of melodies, borrowed from Western popular music.

Clearly, the genesis of structures like Western "harmonic minor" in non-Western cultures must have occurred on melodic rather than harmonic basis. Hence, we need a different term to refer to such modal structures – a term that would highlight not harmonic but melodic origin of the characteristic interval of the augmented second. Jewish, Arabic, Turkish and Persian people enjoy its sound in purely melodic implementation.

Answering this need, a distinguished Russian music theorist, Yuri Kholopov, introduced the new class of *hemiolic* modes – from Greek "*hemiolia*" [i.e., the 1½:1 ratio] – named so in reference to the intervallic ratio between the tones of the augmented second that they systemically engage in melodic motifs and phrases (Kholopov 1988, 38). There could be a number of such augmented seconds in a single mode: e.g., so-called "Hungarian scale" (A-B-C-D#-E-F-G#) contains two hemiolas (C-D# and F-G#).

There are a few important theoretic reasons for adopting Kholopov's classification.

First, unlike the Western harmonic minor, the hemiolic ratio in non-European music systems is *not* a byproduct of temporary *alteration* of a degree for some harmonic reasons. Rather, the interval of augmented second serves as a *permanent* marker of modal organization, supporting a characteristic modal intonation that has been a long-time favorite by indigenous musicians and their audiences.

Second, hemiolic modes differ from Western tonality in one extremely important respect – hemiolic scales are fundamentally *non-diatonic*: their tones *cannot* be positioned in a circle of perfect 5ths. Take the "Hungarian scale" (A-B-C-D#-E-F-G#) – only 3 degrees of it form diatonic relations (A-B-E). Its "gapped" tones (C-D# and F-G#) completely fall off the diatonic foundation. They stand as peculiar exaggerated "augmented steps" (larger than normative "whole steps" of the interval of major second), called to generate extra tension and dramatize the unveiling of a melodic line. Therefore, hemiolic modes differ from regular diatonic modes by heightened expressivity that finds an outlet in musical genres related to elative and even ecstatic expression (e.g., used to evoke religious bliss or Romantic love).

Hemiolic gaps also differ from gaps in anhemitonic pentatonic music (e.g., "A-C" and "E-G" in a minor pentatonic mode "A-C-D-E-G"). Pentatonic gaps do not contrast regular steps in respect to tonal tension (i.e., "A-C" does not exceed "C-D" in tonal tension – both of them seamlessly merge in a uniform diatonic trichord "A-C-D"), as evident from the fact that a pentatonic musical phrase is often terminated by the pentatonic gap. Pentatony, in general, is characterized by overall reduction in tonal tension and greater harmonicity in comparison to heptatony (Bowling and Purves 2015). The succession of pentatonic gaps and steps seamlessly flows from trichord to trichord like the flow of water from one terrace to another (Nikolsky 2015).

The succession of hemiolic gaps and steps, in contrast, generates the opposition of momentary impulses of tension followed by relaxation, where hemiolic expansion requires semitonal shrinking, charging the

melody with immense energy and causing intense energetic fluctuations – which are simply impossible to achieve within a strictly pentatonic melody. Thus, a hemiolic gap "F-G#" contrasts an adjacent semitonal step "E-F". Therefore, whenever both are merged into a hemiolic trichord (E-F-G#), the latter appears not uniform but compound: the augmented second induces a spike in tension, while the semitone releases it. For this reason, hemiolic melodies are rarely terminated by a hemiolic gap – hemiolas as a rule require melodic resolution.

Finally, both tones engaged in a hemiolic gap remain tonally unstable (i.e., they require a melodic continuation that would engage tonally stable degrees of a hemiolic mode. Subsequently, performers habitually exaggerate tonal tension and relaxation by making the upper hemiolic tone slightly sharper and the lower tone slightly lower than required by the standard tuning for a particular musical mode (Marcus 1993) – in order to facilitate the melodic resolution of both gapped tones (e.g., sharpening G# to ascend to A, while flattening F to descend to E). Hemiolic gaps are usually enclosed in the middle of a tetrachord (e.g., F-G# is positioned in the middle of the tetrachord E-F-G#-A), surrounded by stable tones at the margins of a tetrachord (thus, in the example above F-G# are unstable, whereas E and A are stable). Such disposition characterized the Ancient Greek music system (Systema Ametabolon), which most likely was parental to the hemiolic typology of the entire Mediterranean region, as well the Levant and the Central and Middle Asia (Nikolsky 2016a).

This paper introduces a new line of inquiry into the evolutionary lineage of the Ancient Greek music system. It examines the totality of the available evidence, collected from different fields of research, in an attempt to establish the roots of hemiolic typology and construct a perspective view on its relation to the Western tonality.

In search of the origins of hemiolic intervallic typology

Despite the lack of clear historic evidence of origin of the *hemiolic* music, it is quite likely that hemiolic modes, found in modern traditional music of Near East and Central Asia, are descendants of the Ancient Greek tradition (Zannos 1990). Where and how exactly could the transmission have occurred is hard to tell. Pre-Islamic music of Arabs was considerably influenced by the Sabaeans of Harran, especially in transference of the Pythagorean tradition to the "first Peripatetic in Islam," Al-Kindi (Farmer 1925). Sabaeans were in active trade with Greeks in the 5th century BC, when they adopted the Greek numerical notation system (Chrisomalis 2010, 108). It seems plausible that Sabaeans adopted Greek enharmonic music along with the Dionysian cult, associated with this music in Greece: there are indications that the Sabaic national god Almaqah, represented with vine, related to Dionysus, and tradition of wine drinking while listening to music, similar to Greek *symposion*, must have been common in Sheba (Maraqten 1993). The Sabaean colony was discovered at Al-Ula, Dedan, South-West of Egra, testifying that Sabaeans had cultural presence in the North-West Hijaz during Hellenistic times (Nevo 2003, 68).

The region of Hijaz, on the other hand, is known as the cradle of Arabic musical tradition, producing a school that retained its formative influence well into the 12th century AD, while descending from the earlier pre-Islamic *qaynah* school (Touma 1996, 5–12). The *qaynah* culture is remarkably similar to the Greek *symposion*, characterized by its combination of hedonistic appreciation of wine drinking and enjoyment of listening to pleasurable secular music, performed on flute, oboe, and lute by professional entertainers at private parties (Hobden 2013). Such settings were likely to have maintained the cultural ground for Dionysian tradition, from its birth marked by its affiliation with the enharmonic genus of Ancient Greek music (Kowalzig and Wilson 2013).

The microchromatic "shades," employed for expressing the sensual nuances, made enharmonic modes famous for their sophistication and refinement across Hellenic ecumene (Hagel 2009). We should point out that the entire evolution of Ancient Greek *melopoieia* (the art of making melody) is based on the idea of transforming the so-called "Archaic trichord" (E-F-A) by varying the intervallic sizes of its lower and upper constituents (West 1981). The Archaic trichord served as a melodic frame for placement of musical tones, whose exact pitch values were supposed to benefit the expression desired by a music-maker, leading to the establishment of public conventions for tuning of the most popular musical modes – this was the framework for the emergence of two oldest genera of Ancient Greek music, diatonic and enharmonic, credited to Olympus and dated by the 7th century BC (Barker 2007, 165).

This framework put in place a peculiar scheme of tonal organization, where the enharmonic *pyknon* [from Greek word for "pinch"] bundled together three closely positioned pitches separated from the upper tone by a gap. This contrast of microchromatically "shaded" *pyknon* and a gapped tone set the prototype for the later hemiolic modes (Kholopov 1988, 38). It is hard to miss a morphological connection between Ancient Greek enharmonic modes and modern hemiolic modes popular in the same geographic region (Zannos 1990), especially in those modes that require microchromatically adjusted augmented second, such as maqam *Hijaz-Kar-Kurdi* (C-Db-E^{3/4}b-F-G-A^{3/4}b-B^{3/4}b) (Racy 2004, 108).

The Hijaz performance school, founded during the 7-8th centuries, probably inspired the choice of the name for the Hijaz mode, since many earliest modes of maqamat were named after geographic regions (Farmer 1929, 203). Hijaz mode was described by Safi al-Din al-Urmawi in 1293, and was mentioned even 200 years earlier (Neubaer 1992, 597).

The *Hijaz* tetrachord with its augmented 2nd, gave life to the entire "*Hijaz* genre" (using the expression of Habib Hassan Touma, one of the leading specialists in history of maqam music), represented by eight modes that are characterized by the descending pattern of 2nds (minor-augmented-minor) leading to the finalis tone, emulating the hijaz mode (Touma 1996, 33).

Hijaz maqam (after Touma): G-A-B^{1/4}b-C-D-Eb-F³-G-A-Bb-C-D-E-F ascending, and
G-F-E-D-C#-Bb-A-G-F#-Eb-D descending direction.

This *hijaz* mode can be regarded as the backbone for the whole Mediterranean region, penetrating most, if not all, ethnic cultures adjacent to it (Manuel 1989a). This "common" modal construct is defined by Peter Manuel as the "Phrygian tonality", which he considers a product of the interaction of numerous modal traditions of pre-Moorish Spain and Arabic countries and which is expressed by two modes, equivalent to *Bayati* and *Hijaz* maqamat:

Hijaz: E - F - G# - A - B - C^{1/4}# - D up; and E - D - C - B - A - G# - F - E down.

Bayati: E - F^{1/4}# - G - A - B - C - D up; and E - D - C - B - A - G - F^{1/4}# - E down.

1. Audio demonstration: Maqam *Hijaz* G-Ab-B-C-D-E^{1/4}b(Eb)-F-G [\[See Supplementary Audio-1\]](#)
2. Audio demonstration: Maqam *Bayati* G-A^{1/4}b-Bb-C-D-Eb-F-G [\[See Supplementary Audio-2\]](#)

These two modes seem to comprise a system, where their characteristic melodic intonations can interchange within the same work while keeping the mutual harmonic reliance on the "dominant" sound of the "tonic" E, when the latter appears as though it is supporting the upper A, although A does not receive nearly as much stress as E, which clearly acts as finalis in this music (Manuel 1986). The model for such integration seems to come from the practice of modulation from a hemiolic to a diatonic tetrachord/pentachord in maqamat.

3. Audio demonstration: *Nouba Hijaz*. The hemiolic *Hijaz* mode D-Eb-F#-G-A-B^{1/4}b-C keeps alternating with the diatonic *Ajam* mode G-A-B-C-D-E-F. [\[See Supplementary Audio-3\]](#)

Dominant keys vs. Tonic keys

In 1951, Igor Sposobin proposed to qualify such modes as a special group of “*dominant modes*” due to the peculiar role of the systemic tonicization of seemingly unstable tone. These modes have relatively weak I degree (tonic) and unusually strong IV degree – hence their collective title “dominant” suggests that their I degree executes the function of “dominant” towards the IV degree.

Sposobin listed four of such modes, all united by their special feature of comprising a “dominant” relation towards the IV degree minor triad (Sposobin 1969, 101):

- 1) E-F-G-A-B-C-D-E (minor diatonic),
- 2) E-F-G#-A-B-C-D-E (hemiolic),
- 3) E-F-G#-A-B-C-D#-E (double-hemiolic) and
- 4) E-F#-G#-A-B-C-D-E (major diatonic).

This mutual “minor” coloring of the implied “tonic” chord on the IV degree (A-C-E), along with the inverted tonic/dominant functionality and propensity to terminate the musical sentences/sections with the “Phrygian cadence” (IV6-V), whenever arranged in homophonic fashion, these three factors consolidate all four modes into a *single key*.

4. Audio demonstration: *Solea*, Andalusia. The typical example of interchangeability of the melodic tetrachords and triads built in 4 modes: Bb-C-D-Eb-F-Gb-Ab-Bb, Bb-Cb-D-Eb-F-Gb-Ab-Bb, Bb-Cb-D-Eb-F-(Gb)-A-Bb and Bb-Cb-Db-Eb-F-Gb-Ab-Bb. [\[See Supplementary Audio-4\]](#)

Any of these four modes can easily interchange with another within a section of a musical composition, and even a musical phrase – in a way similar to how the minor key in Western tonality can house 3 modes: natural, harmonic, and melodic.

Of course, such “modulations” are most pronounced in the music that is arranged in a homophonic manner.

5. Audio demonstration: Hajibeyov – *Sensiz* (Without you). The dominant key is retained throughout most of the song, with the modes E-F#-G#-A-B-C-D#, E-F#-G#-A-B-C#-D, E-F#-G#-A-B-C-D, E-F-G#-A-B-C-D and E-F#-G-A-B-C-D# (except a little episode in relative minor C#-D#-E-F#-G#-A-B#). The key signatures in the score indicate E major. [\[See Supplementary Audio-5\]](#)
6. Audio demonstration: Mussorgsky – *Nad Rekoj* (Over the river). The dominant key sustains throughout the entire composition that is notated in C# major. The modes include C#-D#-E#-F#-G#-A-B, C#-D-E#-F#-G#-A#-B, C#-D-E-F#-G#-A#-B, C#-D-E-F#-G-A-B, C#-D#-E#-F#-G#-A#-B, C#-D#-E-F#-G#-A-B# and C#-D-E-F#-G#-A-B#. [\[See Supplementary Audio-6\]](#)
7. Audio demonstration: Bizet – *Andaluza* (Entr’acte to Act IV of Carmen). Although the music is notated in D minor, it remains in the dominant key of A from the beginning to the very end, involving the following modes: A-Bb-C#-D-E-F-G, A-Bb-C-D-E-F-G, A-B-C#-D-E-F-G and A-B-C#-D-E-F-G#. [\[See Supplementary Audio-7\]](#)

Three examples above illustrate the use of the “dominant key” in the musical arrangement of traditional Persian poetry (a *ghazal* by Nizami), an art song of the Western classical music, and a symphonic arrangement of a flamenco tune. They all feature homophonic texture, which highlights the hierarchic vertical harmonic organization and tells them apart from the earlier example of the Hijaz mode.

The question whether an orthodox maqam implementation can constitute a “dominant key” should be left for the maqam theorists to answer. Uzeir Hajibeyov, one of the founders of the music theory of

mugam (Azerbaijani music system derivative of *maqam*), wrote: "There is a view that if harmony is applied to naturally monophonic Azerbaijan music, all its modal peculiarities will be reduced to zero. It is quite true. Clumsy application of harmony to Azerbaijan melodies may change their character, neutralize the distinction of their modal peculiarities and even make them rough and vulgar" (Gadjibekov 1957, 32). In this light, the dominant keys might be regarded as the product of applying vertical harmony of the Western music to the modes of Maghrebic, Near Eastern and Central Asian traditional music.

What is obvious here though is that whenever the texture becomes more complex than monody, and especially if chords are used in the musical arrangement, the characteristic features of the "dominant key" perceptually stand out – in music that otherwise might come from very distant cultural traditions. The triads on the I, VII and IV degrees (in the order of reducing functional importance) are the most prominent markers in harmonic progressions in such a key, with the I triad emphasized metrically the most, and the IV triad used sparingly, on weaker metric time, not to overthrow tonicity of the I triad.

Major inclination of the I triad is important in stressing hierarchic superiority of the I degree over the IV degree that houses a *minor* triad in this mode: major tonality is known to be more psychologically stable than minor tonality. This has been established by empirical research (Vuvan and Schmuckler 2011), as well as the historic tradition of music theory, ever since Zarlino formulated major and minor triads in 1558 (Lester 1977) – reflected in his choice of titles "major" versus "minor." The "dominant key" can house the major VI (E-F#-G#-A-B-C#-D in Hajibeyov), but it is usually not supported by the major triad on the IV degree, acting more like a chromatic melodic alteration.¹

Keep in mind that my generalization highlights only the features characteristic for the identity of a dominant key. In reality, the vertical harmonic content in the examples above contains many more harmonies and harmonic relations. Especially Mussorgsky's romance is extremely rich in generating fresh sounding progressions of vertical harmonies. Bizet's arrangement also features brief modulation from "dominant A major" to F major, as well as Hajibeyov's modulation from "dominant E major" to C# minor.

Nevertheless, on the whole, the dominant key definitely maintains its own "sound," identified by ear through its reverted tonic/dominant functionality (shaded by the major/minor contrast) and the prevalent Phrygian cadences, while noticeable absence or near absence of the harmonic progressions alternative to Phrygian. Hajibeyov's work is the most exemplary of the dominant key functionality, where the harmonic progressions are reduced to rather a single Phrygian formula which functions more like a harmonic "drone" throughout extended portions of the score. Similar implementation can be found in almost all examples of flamenco music.

It seems that the "dominant key" should be considered as integration of two different intervallic typologies in relation to the same modal skeleton – something very similar to the practice of application of different genera onto the same *harmonia* in Ancient Greek theory. Compare the way in which Greek Dorian tetrachord generated three generic versions:

- diatonic E-F-G-A,
- chromatic E-F-Gb-A, and
- enharmonic E-F $\frac{1}{4}$ b-G $\frac{3}{4}$ b-A,

to the way the upper tetrachord of Sposobin's "dominant key" generates three versions:

¹ If major VI receives a dedicated harmonization, then it is usually an inversion of the IV triad rather than the triad itself – as evident in the Hajibeyov's score (<http://uzeyir.musigi-dunya.az/ru/sensiz.html>).

- two diatonic - E-F-G-A and E-F#-G#-A, and
- one hemiolic – E-F-G#-A.

Both schemes seem to share the same *modus operandi*.

Hellenistic roots of the hemiolic intervallic typology

Hemiolic/diatonic bifunctionality is extremely pronounced in flamenco music. A number of specialists suggest the origin of this bifunctionality to lie in the Greek *systema teleion* – marking its pronounced proneness to the descending harmonic resolution as the indicator of the Greek origin (Shulze and Skiera 1990). The flamenco music could have imported Greek organization through Arabic or/and Roman mediation, both of which left a mark on Spanish culture in opposition to the Ecclesiastic line of diatonic influence (Sanlucar, Whitehead, and Alcantara-Rojas 2011).

Another possible route of cultural interaction could have occurred through the crystallization of the Andalusian cadences under the influence of the Byzantine liturgical music, which was preserved by the Mozarabic church in Cordoba until the 13th century – such route of cultural import crossed Sicily (Thompson 1985). Notably, Sicilian folk music contains cadences very similar to Andalusian cadences: e.g., the diatonic dominant mode in the song “*A la campagnola*” and the melodic dominant mode with chromatic alterations in the song “*Sirbi*” (Garofalo 1995). The likely source for such influence was the musical system of the Sicilian-Albanian liturgical repertoire – the latter is strictly modal in tonal organization and generally agrees with the Byzantine theory of *oktoechos* (Garofalo 2004).

Kliment Kvitka provided one of the most comprehensive reviews of the literature on the distribution of hemiolic modes in his essay “On the descent of chromaticism in the music of Slavic peoples” - tracing modern folk hemiolic modes to Ancient Greece (Kvitka 1971, 1:312–325). His expert opinion on the Slavic tradition is of special value in light of a new sociological theory claiming that the hemiolic intervallic type to be of folk Slavic origin (Pennanen 2008), while its author seems to be unaware of Kvitka’s research.

Medieval Arabic treatises demonstrate their authors’ familiarity with Platonic, Aristotelian, and Euclidian music theory (Rosenthal 1966), as well as Pythagorean and Aristoxenian – all of which did cause a following amongst Arabic music theorists (Farmer 1930). Greek genera were appropriated in Arabic music and acquired their own semantic denotations: chromatic was associated with the expression of “generosity, freedom, and courage,” while enharmonic - with “mournfulness, grief, and reservedness,” according to Al-Khwarizmi, 10th century (Farmer 1925).

The idea of unity of astronomic, alchemic and medical fields, where numerical proportions embedded in musical modes would be viewed as having power to affect the listeners’ physiological state, was pivotal for medieval Arabic and Persian views on music (Pacholczyk 1996), and the notion of ethos (*ta'tir*) still remains very important as of today (Cohen and Katz 2006, 20). It is quite possible that the idea of diversifying the ethos of a musical mode by means of changing its genus could have attracted attention of Arabic and Persian musicians during Middle Ages and forged their musical thinking in terms of gapped versus diatonic models of *melopoeia*. Following the poor distinction between chromatic and enharmonic genera in Ancient Greek practice (West 1992, 255), Arabic and Persian implementations could also have observed soft transitions between the exact size of the gap, thereby reducing three genera to just 2 in musical practice (against their theoretic distinctions).

Today, hemiolic structure can still be found combined with microtonal inflections of the degrees of a mode, such as in Tminojo and Shbi'oyo modes of the Syrian chant (Lundberg 1997).

8. Audio demonstration: *B'utho*, Supplication by St. Ephraim, Syrian Orthodox chant, Tminoio mode. Chromatic alterations with microtonal inflections: A-Bb-Cb-D(Db)-Eb-F-Gb(G)-Ab(A)-Bb-Cb-Db (see Nikolsky 2016b for the discussion). [[See Supplementary Audio-8](#)]

The Greek Orthodox music theory, following the Chrysanthos reform, adopted the tuning standard for the enharmonic genus that was reserved primarily for the 3rd mode – defining it as concisely as the Ancient Greek theorists did in their treatises, although implemented with slight difference, divorcing the ascending and descending varieties of enharmonic genus to two different tetrachords (Chrysanthos and Rōmanou 1973, 105–108).

9. Audio demonstration: *Kekragion* (a short proper troparion), prefaced by the demonstration of the enharmonic and diatonic genera of the 3rd mode. The augmented 2nd constitutes the modal intonation I-II (here Eb-F#), especially in the ascending direction. [[See Supplementary Audio-9](#)]

However, the exact amount of microtonal adjustments in the practice of modern performers of maqam-based traditions seems to lack strict adherence to any consistent rules formulated by music theorists (Bozkurt et al. 2009). In the tradition of maqamat, the augmented 2nds are usually tweaked by the performers who stretch or shrink them in order to exaggerate the melodic tension or relaxation of the ascending or descending melodic intonation (Marcus 1993). Then, indeed, in practice, a musician faces only binary choice of intervallic typology: whether or not to resort to the gapped or diatonic genera.

It is quite reasonable to assume that the hemiolic intervallic typology is a simplified derivative of chromatic/enharmonic genera of Ancient Greek music system, defined along the same line of opposition to a more “normative” diatonic genus. Of course, the semantic affiliations of the hemiolic modes would substantially vary between different cultures. However, hemiolic melic characteristics seem to demonstrate substantial uniformity across surprisingly wide array of territories: Andalusia, Maghreb, Palestine, Mesopotamia, Turkey, Greece, Balkan, entire Central Asia, most of Middle Asia, reaching India, plus transnational Gypsy and Jewish traditions.

The famous association of Gypsy music with the interval of augmented 2nd, often qualified as “harmonic minor” or “double-harmonic minor” (if it also uses the high IV degree in minor key), should be reconsidered as the heritage of a much more ancient Indo-Arian culture – very similar hemiolic modal structures have been recorded in Calcutta in 1902 (Hornbostel 1975, 1:158–168).

The concept of Mediterranean tonality

Peter Manuel proposes a good umbrella term for the “dominant family” of diatonic/gapped modes – calling it “*the Mediterranean tonality*” (Manuel 1989a). This term accurately reflects the distinct opposition of the music produced within the conceptual framework of the tonality based on “dominant keys” to that of the Western tonality. The ongoing influence of the latter seems to put in place “commercial” forms of the Mediterranean tonality, which appear inauthentic in their artistic expression to indigenous population (Manuel 1989b).

Similar influences and rejections must have occurred in the past as well. Thus, the mainstream music culture, propagated by the Western Catholic Church in the late Middle Ages, found itself in opposition to the types of music that formed the foundation for the emergence of Mediterranean tonality, an example of which is Andalusian *Cante Jondo* that preceded *Cante Flamenco* (Sanlucar, Whitehead, and Alcantara-Rojas 2011). Barbara Thompson points out that the existing flamenco tradition is, in fact, a joined product of co-influence of Gypsy, Arab, Jewish, and Indian ethnic cultures (Thompson 1985) – all frowned upon by the Western ecclesiastical authorities. Hence, we can safely conclude that the

official Catholic music met general resistance on the part of indigenous population of medieval Spain despite all attempts of local authorities to popularize this music and make its tonal organization canonic for all forms of music, including the secular forms.

Certainly, Western influence was one of the factors that shaped the Mediterranean tonality when it started reaching international acclaim in the 18th century: the Hijaz-like melodic intonations, including the microtonal inflections, were placed against the accompaniment based on the alternating triads of Western music, whose tonic-dominant functionality defined the chordal axis for this new international type of music. However, even the explicit use of triadic chords to accompany hemiolic melodies does not turn such music into a key of Western tonality, because the hemiolic melody is still conceived in a purely modal fashion – without any trace of progressions of “implied chords” which governs *melopoeia* in Western tonality.

Implied chords are immediately obvious in the makeup of many popular melodies of Western classical music. Such is the theme of a famous waltz by Johann Strauss Jr., “*On the beautiful blue Danube*”. Each of its melodic phrases clearly outlines the triads (e.g., tonic, dominant, etc.), thereby indicating the chords and their changes in harmonic progressions throughout the course of this theme – even if it is performed without any accompaniment at all, as a solo melody, on a completely monophonic instrument, such as flute. The monophonic performance still reveals the implied chords and chordal progressions.

Most Westernized works of Arabic or Persian traditional music employ chords in a manner of a *drone* (which is strongly rooted in Mediterranean tradition). Drone stands as a tonicizing combination of tones, prevalent in the support of melody, only occasionally diversified by brief use of what Western music theory qualifies as the “applied dominant” chord (it would be more accurate to regard it as “an interrupted drone” rather than a harmonic function), where heterophonic organization in texture outweighs any homophonic contribution of chords (Nettl 1972).

According to Peter Manuel (Manuel 1989a), the first documentation of Mediterranean tonality came rather late, circa 1830s, and had to do with the growing popularity of the piano home music in Romania, inspiring adaptation of “Turkish” chromatic style to the broken chordal accompaniment (in the form of so-called “Alberti figuration”). Samples of such music are perpetuated in manuscripts of “linear notation” for piano. Creators of these manuscripts were aware of their “Westernized” style, apparently seeing it as culturally prestigious. Growing popularity of their adaptations probably set the precedence for similar treatment of “Turkish”-style ensemble music, supplying the traditional chromatic melodies with chords.

International prestige of orchestral music and Western musical instruments must have motivated local musicians to assimilate Western system of chords, which had a “quantization” effect on microtonal inflections, eventually causing their reduction and even disappearance. Thus, more modern implementations of the Mediterranean tonality are often tonally “simplified”: they come totally free from micro-chromaticism.

10. Audio demonstration: *Doina si Sirba*, Bucharest, Romania. This is an example of hemiolic music conceived in the “dominant mode” D-E-F#-G-A-Bb-C#-D-E-F, with a pronounced drone functionality of the G minor triad, performed by the brass band, recorded in 1905. [[See Supplementary Audio-10](#)]

Diatonic vs. chromatic music and hypermodal music as a golden mean for Christian ideology

The ancient opposition of diatonic and chromatic music that sparked such fiery debates in the 5th century BC Athens (Csapo 2004), re-emerged once again during the Middle Ages to fuel the divergence between the Mediterranean and Western tonalities some time during the Middle Ages.

For a long time, Western European music was isolated from the cultures, where "Mediterranean tonality" had been forming, by the grip of the ban imposed by Christian authorities in countries of Christendom. Christian ideology was extremely hostile towards Pagan professional music from the times of the earliest Christians, reaching its peak during the early Middle Ages. Especially prohibitive was the attitude towards the instrumental and, even more so, Hellenistic chromatic music.

Thus, St. Clement of Ohrid alarmed against "tenderizing harmonies with their refined decorations, which covertly instill in people's minds addiction to luxury and dissoluteness" (Shestakov 1966, 97). Clement of Alexandria equated chromatic music with drunkenness and prostitution (Herms et al. 2007, 2:249) – probably aiming at the association of chromatic genus with music performed at *symposion*. Clement's treatise, *Logos Christology*, included an account of musical cosmology based on the Babylonian/Pythagorean philosophy of the "music of the spheres" (Cosgrove 2006), but censoring its theory according to the Christian dogmas by reducing harmony to the diatonic genus alone, ignoring the chromatic and enharmonic genera of Antiquity.

St. Augustine of Hippo followed Clement's steps. St. Augustine instituted Christian anthem and prayer as principal forms of practicing Christianity – but restricted them to diatonic modal organization. Greek chromatic intervals were discussed in medieval Western treatises on music theory (Herlinger 2002), but left aside in music practice, primarily because of their complexity – until the Renaissance restored public interest in Ancient Greek culture (Atkinson 2008, 258). Then, influential Vicentino set a goal to re-institute the chromatic genus in order to provide a Renaissance artist with richer palette of expressions (Maniates 1993).²

Before the Renaissance, whenever the Christian music needed more dramatic expression than strict diatony could afford, the *hypermodal* principles of tonal organization were implemented – for the Western Christendom, they were materialized in the Guidonian hexachord system (see Nikolsky 2016c for the discussion). Guidonian organization observed the hypermodal principle of maintaining the modal integrity of the melody while locking B and Bb to different registral positions in order to prevent their so-called "false relation" (i.e., modal contradiction), when both are used in close proximity within the same musical phrase.

In essence, the Guidonian system was based on the idea of fitting a pre-existing tune into that part of the ambitus of a musical mode where the intervallic structure of the tune would not demand chromatic alterations of normative degrees (Bower 2002). This very idea reflects concern for keeping modal integrity, thereby moderating the infusion of tonal tension brought about by the engagement of variants for a few modal, which characterizes hypermodal organization from the alternative methods of tonal organization.

² There is evidence that micro-intervals were still used in early Middle Ages in Europe (Meyer 1996) – but vanished with the advent of the staff notation, as Ferreira points out, probably due to the "quantization" of tuning, prompted by graphic representation on the staff lines (Ferreira 1997, 160–289).

However, the hypermodal trends did not find fertile ground in Western Europe, whose music headed in a completely different direction after the Great Western Schism of 1378. Eastern Orthodox Church adopted the hypermodal model, whereas Western Catholic Church endorsed the progressive chromaticization of the Guidonian system by legitimizing the theory of "*musica ficta*." Gradually, Western composers became attracted to the idea of using chains of modulations from mode to mode in order to musically "illustrate" changes in liturgical text (Powers and Wiering 2001).

The same approach became the favorite tool of composers of Ars Nova in treating secular vocal music (Tischler 1999). Secular art songs, especially the ones in vernacular languages, combined multiple modes in the same tune to a much greater extent than concurrent plainchant. Also, polyphonic songs often featured different texts (sometimes in different languages) and different modes for simultaneous parts. From vocal music, the practice of ongoing modulations penetrated instrumental forms of music, since throughout the Middle Ages vocal parts were routinely delegated to musical instruments, whenever there was shortage in qualified singers or the comprehensibility of text in a complex polyphonic setting became an important issue (Everist 2011). As a result of frequent modulations, Western music started heavily using chromatic alterations.

Western and Eastern standards of musical composition started diverging much earlier than the Great Western Schism. Already in the 8th century AD, Carolingian art became more permissive towards emotional expression than the Orthodox canons of concurrent Byzantine culture. Subsequently, Gregorian chant made frequent use of modulations and alterations justified by the necessity to highlight the meaning of the liturgical words (Heckenlively 1900, 52).

11. Audio demonstration: "*Astiterunt reges terrae*," Antiphon for Good Friday, modulation involving the hard switch from minor 3rd (A-C) to major 3rd (A-C#). [[See Supplementary Audio-11](#)]

Acceptance of such modulations in otherwise quite rigorous early Christian music could be explained by its peculiar semantic effect that met the preferences of the Carolingian aesthetics. Modulations obscure the gravitational map of the music work, and make the chant appear more "ethereal"³ – *free of worldly gravity*. The word "gravitational" here refers to the harmonic aspect of tonal organization in music that deals with the resolution of harmonic tension, expressed in the tendency of certain pitch classes to "resolve" into the other pitch classes within a musical mode, thereby forming the antithesis of "unstable" versus "stable" tones. Steve Larson conveniently conceptualized their opposition as a "gravitational model" of tonal organization (2012), providing the experimental evidence in support for existence of "musical gravity" (Larson & Vanhandel 2005). The psychophysiological roots for experiencing "gravitational forces" according to Larson's model might explain the wide spread of the opposition of "stable" and "unstable" pitch classes across world's music cultures (Alekseyev 1986).

³ This effect must have been explored yet by the Ancient Greeks. It has to do with the perceptual phenomenon that tones that are more frequently repeated (Aarden 2003) and assigned longer time values (Smith & Schmuckler 2004), in music not conforming to Western tonality (Cuddy 1997), are perceived as more stable (Bharucha 2002) proportional to their frequency of repetition (Krumhansl 1990, 67). Such tones also are remembered better than the unstable tones (Krumhansl 1979). According to Stefan Hagel (in personal communication), the amount of chromatic/enharmonic tones probably exceeded the amount of diatonic tones in Ancient Greek dramatic arias around the 4th century BC, and especially in spondeion piping. Such music must have manifested to the contemporary audiences a noticeably different gravitational style, making the musical modes significantly less memorable, and reducing gravity in the modal anchors. Once forged, such music could have won appreciation in the neighboring folk cultures of the Near East, and survived there, impressing the visiting Carolingian authorities with their exotic sound.

Weightlessness was expressed not only in the Medieval chant but in the ecclesiastical architecture of High Middle Ages: evident in the flying buttress, Gothic arch, and ribbed vault – all as though denying gravity, eager to ascend to the skies. The emergence of these traits is traceable to the 11th century Islamic influences on the Roman legacy in Western Europe, more pronounced on the Italian soil, as opposed to the traditional affiliation of Gothic spirit with France (Kluckert 2004).

Similar justification, although implemented differently, is evident in the Eastern Orthodox *kalophonic chant* (Stathis 2014), often described in terms of its weightlessness. Denial of tonal gravity here was apparently regarded as a feature that distinguished the "Heavenly" ecclesiastic music from its "Earthly" secular counterpart (Martynov 1994, 123).

Weightlessness, achieved by means of modulation, became the preferred manner of the "dispersed" gravitational style adopted by the Western plainchant. Some chants even made the task of modal identification problematic for composers and music scholars: in early 10th century, Abbot Regino of Priim was complaining that some antiphons started in one mode, continued in another and ended in a third (Hiley 1990). Neither Frankish nor Old Roman repertoires seemed to have followed strict modal classification comparable to Byzantine *oktoechos*.

Greater liberty in modulation was to some extent regulated after the 13th century in the West, yet still exceeded much more conservative attitude to modulation and chromaticism in the contemporaneous Eastern orthodox churches. This is despite the fact that Western plainchant remained rather "frozen" in keeping the limits for how far chromaticism was allowed to go – staying immune to advents of manneristic "chromatic styles" in Western polyphonic music and earning reputation of somewhat culturally deficient music comparing to the art music of a time. To get an idea of how far medieval Western composers could advance in their creative exploration of chromaticism, listen to this composition by Solage.

12. Audio demonstration: Solage – "*Fumeux fume par fume*" (c.1370s). Remarkably intense chromatic polyphony presents a moody, garrulous, irascible and melancholic character, suggesting the simile between the waiving chromatic melodic lines and heavy smoke that prevents clear vision (Unruh 1983). Just the opening sing-out of the first word "fumeux" engages 11 chromatic tones: G, A, Bb, B, C, Db, D, Eb, E, F and F#. [\[See Supplementary Audio-12\]](#)

Eventually, Gregorian chant ended up by defaulting back to its original state through the reform that restituted the conservative principles in the so-called Solesmes style in the 19th century (Combe 2008).

Chromatic music in the West and in the East and their relation to hemiolic modes

Eastern plainchant followed diametrically opposite historic path in its attitude towards chromatic music and gravity. By the 19th century most Eastern orthodox churches embraced chromaticism as well as hemiolic modes (Lind 2012, 68), viewing it as a restoration of the conservative Classic Ancient Greek doctrine of ethos (at this historic point viewed positively by Eastern bishops), along with the official adoption of *ison* (the practice of adding a drone part to a canonic melody) for plainchant performance and notation (Koço 2015).

Weightlessness, achieved by means of melismatic ornamentation and modularity of the melic structures that carried idiosyncratic modal features, became the preferred manner of "intertwining" a melodic line in the Eastern plainchant of the late Middle Ages.

In contrast, Western Christianity never allowed the use of decidedly non-diatonic hemiolic modes. The only Orthodox Church that allowed neither any chromaticism nor hemiolas in plainchant was Russian Church (Kutuzov 2008, 43–51).

An important point of difference is that Western medieval music did not actually restore the Ancient Greek system of chromatic modulations – despite the veneration of the Greeks by early Renaissance pioneers in the 15th century. Unlike the Eastern restitution of Ancient Greek music theory in the 19th century Greece, Western theory of chromatic music grew anew, driven mainly by the development of polyphony after the 12th century. Its base was laid by the elaboration of “false relation” by reproducing the legitimate hexachord-like mutations from different tetrachords (Atkinson 2008, 129).

The notion of "chromatic" lost its ancient denotation of a harmonic genus and was understood merely as an aberration from the diatonic norm. Music, made without chromatic tones, received the title "*musica recta*" (proper music), and the progressions that involved chromatic tones were referred to as "*musica ficta*" (contrived music), looked upon as an imperfection necessary for writing good-sounding polyphony (Tischler 1973).

While chromaticism, disqualified from the status quo of a specific genus into a mere “accidental” (indeed performed by accident, not always in the same way, to the performer’s liking), was gradually evolving into what ended up as chromatic tonality by the 17th century (Dahlhaus 2014), the old-Greek style chromatic modes were reinstated in the Christian East. Already in the 13th century, Byzantine chant included an unofficial chromatic mode (Beaton 1980).

Ever since the late Middle Ages, Greek secular music was assimilating tonal structures coming from maqamat, and since the 17th century this process started making an imprint on the Orthodox church music (Zannos 1990). A similar development occurred in the neighboring Orthodox Churches. Thus, in Romanian chant the diatonic Second Mode of the Oktoechos E-F-G-A-B-C-D was officially replaced with the hemiolic M-F-G#-A-B-C-D (Moisil 2011) – with similar substitutions in Bulgarian and Serbian chant.

13. Audio demonstration: My soul, Bulgarian chant, Second mode, hemiolic adaptation. Instead of the canonic diatonic G-Ab-Bb-C-D-Eb-F, prescribed for the Second mode by the *Octoechos*, here the hemiolic mode G-Ab-B-C-D-Eb-F is used. [[See Supplementary Audio-13](#)]

If “Greek” music style planted hemiolic music in the Eastern plainchant, “Moorish” style exported it to Spain (Farmer 1963). As the new Spanish style was gaining popularity in the West, so did Spanish hemiolic modes – especially through the global spread of guitar music that originated from Spain (Manuel 1986). Flamenco music that came into limelight in the 18th century exhibits traits that can be traced back to Ancient Greek music treatises (Sanlucar, Whitehead & Alcantara-Rojas 2011), and so do mountaineer’s Balkan cultures – including their affinity with micro-intervals (Petrović 1994).

Gypsy music bridged Europe with Indian traditional music (Hornbostel 1975, 1:168) – yet another source of hemiolic intervallic typology and microtonal inflections (Kvitka 1971, 1:326-330). India could be considered the Southern Asian border of the area affected by the Ancient Greek influence, brought there by the conquest of Alexander the Great.

An alternative source of hemiolic music across the globe provided the Hebrew chant once it absorbed the Greek and Arabic modal principles (Subirats 2006). Its most popular hemiolic “*Ahava rabbah gust*” mode and “*Mi Shebeirach gust*” mode both constituted the *nusach* of a prayer service (Engel 1904).

The resultant habitat of hemiolic modes is enormously vast: Kvitka (1971, 1:313–316) lists Italian, French, Basque, Danish, Swedish, Norwegian, German, Finnish, Scottish, Polish, Slovak, Romanian,

Greek, Hungarian, Ukrainian, Belorussian folk musics as importers of hemiolic modes, not to forget the post-Renaissance classical music of the West and both Americas.

Hemiolic structure easily coexists with chromatic tendencies due to modulations encouraged by plagal relations, i.e. A-B-C-D-E-F-G#-A (tonic A) in ascending motion, and A-G-F#-E-D#-C-B-A (tonic E) in descending. In his study of Synagogal music, Mikhail Gnesin had examined musical modes in conjunction with expressive tuning practice, and found that five out of six most common Hebrew modes often engaged modulations, to the extent that the mode itself could be called "modulating" – and include enharmonic stylization by the use of microtones (Zemtsovsky 2012). Similar "modulating" oscillations between two modal anchors, each grounding its own subset of hierarchically organized pitch classes, with the characteristic satellite chromatic tones, can be found in Balkan orthodox chants.

14. Audio demonstration: "*Holy Spirit*," Serbian chant. Modulating hemiolic inflections between low C (C-Db-E-F-G-Ab-B-C) and higher F (F-G-Ab-Bb-C-Db) are chromatically enriched (the C subset with F#, and the F subset with A, B, and D natural) throughout this hymn, with both tones used as the finalis. [\[See Supplementary Audio-14\]](#)

Such organization inherits centripetal gravity of *multiple* anchors from Ancient chromatic system. One consequence of habituation to such a system is great refinement of interval detection. Experimentally, it was shown that reference to the chromatic scale prior to the task of identification of melodic intervals increases the acuity in interval estimation while reducing tonicity in perceived pitches – in contrast to reference to the diatonic scale (Tszuzaki 1991). Greater acuity leads to greater variability in expressive tuning: performers have an incentive to emphasize intervallic differences between different degrees of a musical modes, so the chromatic genera that feature the richest interval set also have the greatest deviations from standard tuning (Delviniotis, Kouroupetroglou & Theodoridis 2008).

Chromatic coloration can be extremely intense in Mediterranean tonality, serving as the principle means of *melopoeia* – bypassing the diatonic anchors altogether.

15. Audio demonstration: "*Glory, Through the Prayers of St. Sava*," Serbian chant. Chromatic pitch set of: E-F-F#-G-G#-A-B-C. [\[See Supplementary Audio-15\]](#)

What unites Mediterranean tonality with the Ancient Greek chromatic system is their mutual reliance on the *clustering principle*: the entire pitch set of a musical system is divided in near-equal-size component subsets (tetrachords/trichords), and each obtains a *pyknon* zone, where the altered tones are squeezed together to generate "abnormal" tension – while leaving the rest of the subset comfortably spaced.

16. Audio demonstration: Turkish makam *Beste-Nigar* performed on saz lute. This composition features the *pyknon* (F#-G-Ab) that plays an important role in the melody by generating much tension in the center of its ambitus: B-C#-D-E-F#-G-Ab-B-C-D-Eb-F#. [\[See Supplementary Audio-16\]](#)

Majority of examples of chromatic Mediterranean tonality, with or without microtonal coloration, are based on *tetrachordal* divisions and microtonal intonation-driven alterations of the intra-tetrachordal degrees.

17. Audio demonstration: "*Let Every Breath*," Greek chant, Macedonia. Characteristic modal intonations that include major/minor 3rd in two tetrachords, on G and D. [\[See Supplementary Audio-17\]](#)

There is a line of inheritance that links Mediterranean tonality with non-octave hypermode through the employment of the "chain principle" of stitching together different modal subsets (trichords, tetrachords and/or pentachords), which can occur in variety of ways (Sachs 1960). The most common techniques

are disjunct and conjunct connection (Beliayev 1990). However, occasionally, more complex techniques are used: e.g., double-conjunct connection that shares 2 mutual tones between two adjacent subsets, as it takes place between the *Segah*, *Saba*, and *Chargah* tetrachords in the *Beste-Nigar* makam of Turkish traditional music (Audio Demonstration No.15).

The similarity between Mediterranean tonality and hypermode probably originates from their common ancestry in the Ancient Greek "Perfect System." Whenever the modal subsets turn out to comprise the "false relation" between the subsets' lower and upper parts, a maqam obtains the characteristic "hypermodal" sound: its upper zone tends to accumulate tension, while its lower zone often houses greater relaxation, most evident in cadences.

18. Audio demonstration: Maqam *Saba* on oud solo. The lowest tetrachord *Saba* (built on D) overlaps with the tetrachord *Hijaz* (on F), and receives another disjointed tetrachord *Hijaz* (on C), forming a 10-tone mode D-Eb-F-Gb-A-Bb-C-Db-E-F, with false relationship between higher and lower D's (diminished octave) and E's (augmented octave). [\[See Supplementary Audio-18\]](#)

Typical hypermodal elasticity of tension can exist in hemiolic tetrachords chained together.

19. Audio demonstration: Cherubic Hymn, Greek chant, First Mode. The increase in tension for ascending melodic motion by the degrees of a non-octave mode that incorporates two hemiolic upper tetrachords: (B)-C-D-E(Eb) + F-Gb-A-Bb(B) + C-Db-E-F. [\[See Supplementary Audio-19\]](#)

However, registral build-up of tension towards the trebles remains a secondary trait of tonal organization for the hemiolic modes, which inside of tetrachords operate very much like the Ancient Greek chromatic genera. The primary energy source for a hemiolic melody remains the maximization of tonal tension within a tetrachord: the gapped tones repel each other, while becoming more attracted to the marginal anchor tones. This tendency essentially manifests the same gravitational force as that observed in the chromatic modulations in Ancient Greek music: they both take advantage of the heptatonic approach to harmony – generating greater tension to obtain greater resolution (Nikolsky 2015).

Distribution of tonal gravity in keys of Ancient Greek, Mediterranean and Western music systems

Inequality in distribution of "shaded" and "lightened" zones across the entire ambitus of a music system increases anchoring in each subset by stressing subordination relations between its tones. In Ancient Greek music system, *phthongoi kinoumenoi* ("movable" notes - chromatic tones in the middle of a tetrachord) were subordinate to *phthongoi hestotes* ("fixed" - marginal tones), and coordinated to one another; whereas *hegemon* (the highest tone) was considered prime in a tetrachord that thereby acquired two levels in hierarchy of stability (Kholopov 2006, 71). Ancient Greeks seem to have been the first to distinguish musical tones in regard to their stability or instability in their music theory. We shall keep referring to this aspect of tonal organization as "gravitational", since objects reveal if they are stable or unstable under the influence of gravity.

Unstable tones were also hierarchically related: the upper unstable tones (*lichanos*) could subordinate to one another (*parhypate*), especially when both were at the bottom of a modally transposed tetrachord (*barypyknoi*). Such subordination probably originated from greater permanence in tuning of the *parhypate*: it maintained its tuning across most important genera, diatonic and chromatic, receiving chromatic alteration only in enharmonic genus – while the *lichanos* was altered in every genus.

This chromatic hierarchy, once forged by the Ancient Greeks as a modal principle of *melopoeia*, set the model for both, Western tonality and Mediterranean tonality. Tonal keys are characterized by such organization where less stable non-diatonic tones are attracted to diatonic ones, generating melodic inertia (Krumhansl 1979). The presence of this layer of organization tells tonality from modality (Nikolsky 2015): whenever a musical composition is organized in a modal manner, there must be certain "tendency tones" (melodic intonations that are characteristic for that mode) modally inflected.

Subsequently, chromatic alterations can be encountered only in the advanced music systems based on diatonic families of heptatonic modes (such as Ionian, Aeolian, Lydian, Mixolydian, Dorian and Phrygian modes of Western classical tradition) during modulations. However, even in this case, none of the sister-modes within a family embeds a shared layer of chromatic alterations which would be subordinated to a diatonic layer. Chromatic alterations remain isolated, each existing autonomously for just a single diatonic degree.

Greek chromatic system was the first known documented music system that featured tonal keys. They must have originated in the diatonic system around the 6th century BC: Dorian, Phrygian, and Lydian keys came first, followed by Hypodorian, Hypophrygian, and later, Hypolydian (Hagel 2009, 7). However, these keys, originally quite similar to modern diatonic keys, became tonally convoluted by the chromatic genera, obscuring the gravitational framework of their diatonic anchors. That must have been the reason for a special prestige associated with mastering the chromatic and especially enharmonic genera, and, conversely, responsible for their ultimate decline in the Western Roman Empire. To put it simply, chromatic, and enharmonic keys turned out to be too complex for audiation by a layperson, and therefore yielded to simpler diatonic keys. In this process, the chromatic layer of a key became lost in the West.

In the East, however, this chromatic layer could have survived through conversion into the assortment of trichords, tetrachords and pentachords of different intervallic structures: diatonic, chromatic, as well as microchromatic. These "rasterized" chromatic and enharmonic particles turned into "chunks" of melodic information, serving as melodic "bricks" for construction of musical composition. Having a finite assortment of modal subsets did address the problem of effective audiation, making it possible to process the melodic chunks of various intervallic typology as a harmonic filling of a particular gravitational frame. Eventually, after centuries of exercising the audiation of such chromatic and enharmonic fillings, the new Mediterranean key evolved – where the chromatic and microchromatic layers ended up embedded in the dedicated modal subsets.

At present, Mediterranean tonality is implemented in keys that can feature tonicity on par with Western tonality (extremely strong in *cante flamenco* or in Romanian *doina*) and carry numerous layers of tonal hierarchy. Thus, flamenco implies chords, where root tones constitute a different pitch class than the rest of the chordal tones. Non-chordal tones are widely used as well. Or, neo-Byzantine *oktoechos* affords the use of *ison*, which comprises a discrete layer of anchor tones used in harmonic reference towards the tones of a melody.

The principal difference of Mediterranean keys from Western keys is that the former do not assign the III and V degrees to the tonic function. Instead, Mediterranean keys usually stress the gravity of the IV or V degree through marking the lowest tone of a disjunct or conjunct tetrachord. Their unstable degrees usually have more nuanced intervallic relations and complicated hierarchic ranking than the unstable degrees in the Western tonality.

Musical texture in Western, Mediterranean and Ancient Greek implementations of chromaticism

Throughout all of its implementations, chromatic music incites greater directionality and complexity in melodic motion, as compared to the diatonic music. But hemiolic chromaticism promotes, perhaps, the most complex melodic structures due to richer relations between the unstable degrees in a mode and its dependence of functionality of degrees on the direction of melodic motion, their disposition in the overall ambitus and their place in melodic syntactic structures (such as onset, climax, or end points in a musical phrase).

Such complex system of coordination/subordination charges hemiolic chromatic melody with a heavy load of information – heavier than in a typical melody in Western tonal composition, where directionality, registral position, and position in a phrase do not systemically determine the choice of intervallic values. Heavy compression of melodic information makes it cognitively problematic to dress a Mediterranean melody in a homophonic or polyphonic texture in a manner that is so common to Western classical music.

Centrality of vocal monody - melody whose thematic content receives intricate improvisatory elaboration - has become the landmark of Mediterranean music (Blum 2002). For performers and listeners, its chromatic organization promotes the musical thinking in terms of organicity/inorganicity of specific tones in relation to a given pitch set. Every modulation necessarily involves a tone that would signal that the previous pitch set is no longer functional, and the melody proceeds towards some new unknown pitch set, which the listener should be looking for. "Signal-tones" that manifest the coming of a new musical mode were discussed yet by Cleonides (1st century BC), and are accounted for in the maqam theory (which is derivative from Ancient Greek system) in the capacity of "borrowed note" – i.e., a tone that does not belong to the current pitch set and might supply tonal recoloration (alteration) of a legitimate pitch class or serve as a pivot for modulation (Sultan 1988).

Seyit Yöre (2012) suggests to reserve a special term for the first occurrence of such tones in a musical mode – "alienation" – in distinction from proper modulation and alteration. Karl Signell demonstrates how altering a tone in Turkish makam can execute different tonal functions: establishing the exposition section of a melody; inserting a foreign tone ("borrow a tone") to support or ornament the dominant tone; inserting a foreign tetrachord to diversify and emphasize a passage; stitching different sections together; or generating a compound makam (Signell 1977, 67–112).

Western monody also treated chromatic tones as "alien" to diatonic tones, holding the latter as "natives" to a musical mode. Gregorian chant shared the same theoretic foundation with the early Byzantine chant in its official rejection of chromaticism except the cases of alternations of "B flat" and "B natural" done to avoid the melodic tritone (Heckenlively 1900, 33) – a tradition that probably dates back to the Babylonian music system, notable for its aversion to tritone (Kilmer and Tinney 1996).⁴

However, Western plainchant has stayed quite restrictive in its policies for such "legal aliens." It reserved chromatic alterations mostly for cadential purposes (Homan 1964). In Western secular medieval

⁴ Using tritone as a criterion for definition of a mode immediately brings to mind the theory of modal voicing by Yavorsky (Ewell 2012). Being criticized for the lack of historic support for his theory of tritone as a driving force that directs harmonic resolution within a mode, Yavorsky's ideas might now receive historic confirmation from the Ancient music theories. Thus, Babylonian texts (CBS 10996 and UET VII 74) are explicit in prescribing to leave out the "unclear interval" (triton) at the end, before reaching the octave (Gurney & West 1998) – which clearly singles out the interval of tritone as a primary factor of modal organization.

monody, the use of chromatic alteration was freer – probably due to the absence of religious concerns for emotional moderation. Thus, the musical modes of troubadour and trouvère melodies were frequently modified by chromatic alterations (including also non-B tones, such as C#) for the purposes of beautification (Westrup 1954, 231). Such use should be regarded as a form of intensifying the aesthetic emotion carried by lyrics.

Starting from the 10th century, rise of polyphony in the West radically altered chromatic practices, introducing new rules that mostly had to do with the technicality of combining multiple melodic lines without creating undesirable harmonic intervals (Tischler 1973). Such technique became known under the name of "*musica ficta*." According to it, essentially, chromatic alteration was viewed as an insertion of a foreign tone into an otherwise harmonious diatonic subset of the music system – done quite irrationally, following an aesthetic intuition to contribute a certain character to the melody (Brothers 1997, 11). Therefore, alterations varied from case to case, even between different manuscript copies of the very same composition.

From a harmonic perspective, all these forms of chromatic organization supplied the creator of music with a wide array of options for conceiving an original melodic construct that would demonstrate his craftsmanship while effectively conveying emotional information via a stock of diatonic-based conventions, embellishing this expression with idiosyncratic nexus of chromatic alterations (Listen to Audio example 12, Solage).

To sum things up, it seems that both Western and Eastern chromatic implementations share the heritage of Ancient Greek chromatic music in regard to their affinity with expression of greater tonal tension, associated with communication of aesthetic emotions. However, each of the two implementations directs harmonic organization towards different goals:

- Western music has remained focused on the aspect of vertical harmony (integration of simultaneous tones). The history of this music presents the ongoing process of forging and updating the laws of optimal encoding of *vertical* relations between multiple melodic lines.
- In supporting this goal, chromatic organization never crossed lines of diatonic organization for the most part of Western history – not even in the music that appear the most "chromatic" in its sound, such as Gesualdo's motets, which bombard the listener with all sorts of alterations that make sense only within very distinct modal frames (Sabaino and Mangani 2013).

20. Audio demonstration: Gesualdo – "*Se la mia Morte Brami*", madrigal for 5 voices (1613). The opening sentence "*Se la mia morte brami, crudel, lieto ne moro*" (if you long for my death, cruel one, happily shall I die) contains 11 chromatic tones: G-Bb-D-F-Eb-E-Ab-A-B-C-C#, the 12th tone, F# appearing 4 bars later. [[See Supplementary Audio-20](#)]

The diatonic foundation of Western music became challenged only around the 1920s by the invention of the alternative, purely chromatic, methods of tonal organization (e.g., Schoenberg's dodecaphony).

- In contrast, Eastern hemiolic modes, from their earliest traceable times, have presented a *harmonic system that was alternative to diatonic organization*. The Eastern Orthodox church documents are explicit about that, defining a separate place for diatonic and chromatic, as well as enharmonic implementations (Lind 2012, 68). Each of them was preferable for each specific mode of the oktoechos (Scurtu and Tutu 2011).

The historic development of Mediterranean tonality seems to have proceeded in the direction of greater complexity of intonations, laid into the tetrachordal framework – abstaining from polyphonic and homophonic textures altogether, and zooming into the characteristic expression of a single melodic

stream. Even in music textures that contain an accompaniment, melody receives only limited support from the drone and possible heterophonic inflections of the supporting choir (Koço 2015) or of an accompanying instrument (Ahrens 1973), possibly an ensemble of instruments whose arrangement is usually driven by the idea of dubbing the melody in parallel 4th or 5th (Picken 1953). All in all, Mediterranean key is designed to expose solely one melodic stream, albeit extremely rich in information and often free from patterns of repetition – resembling the model of “stream of consciousness”, most pronounced in the genres of spontaneous vocal improvisation, such as *Mawwāl* or *Qawwāli*.

- The *hemiolic* chromaticism of Eastern cultures nourishes the complexity of structures of *horizontal* harmony that integrates the succeeding tones within the same melodic line.
- The *diatonic* chromaticism of Western classical tradition supports the complexity of *vertical* harmony that integrates the combinations of all the simultaneous tones in all participating parts.

Gravitational characteristics of chromatic trichords, tetrachords and hemiolas

The above-mentioned specializations are determined by the distribution of gravitational function within the modal subsets of a music system:

- Since Western chromaticism was originally *accidental* in nature, it followed the *trichordal* scheme, where the *single* chromatic degree would be jammed between two diatonic degrees (more stable than the chromatic one). Such scheme emphasizes the contrast between even and odd degrees, promoting the triad induction (Mazel 1952). Subsequently, Western chromaticism should be viewed as a driving force behind the general orientation of Western music towards progressive innovation of the expressive means and the criterion of originality held as a standard for aesthetic evaluation of a musical composition and its performance (Nikolsky 2016a).
- Since Mediterranean chromaticism generally followed the *tetrachordal* scheme, where *two* chromatic degrees would be encapsulated between two diatonic degrees (more stable than the chromatic couple). It constituted a *permanent* form of modal organization, it was distinguished from Western chromaticism by greater rigidity in adherence to rules, greater stereotypicity of technical execution and homogeneity of semantic attribution due to stronger reliance on public conventions. Chromatic episodes were determined not so by the fancy of a music-maker (as typical for Western music) but by the concerns for modal integrity of the music (by such contextual factors as melodic direction or intervallic style – e.g., stepwise versus leap).

The pentachordal organization is also possible in Mediterranean modes. Such is the *Nawa Athar* (C-D-Eb-F#-G) pentachord in the maqam theory – it lays the foundation of the entire Nakriz genre (Touma 1996, 34):

Nakriz: B $\frac{1}{4}$ b-C-D-Eb-F#-G-A-Bb-C-D-Eb-F#-G up, and G-F#-Eb-D-C-Bb-A-G-F#-Eb-D-C down.

21. Audio demonstration: Maqam *Nikriz* A-B-C-D#-E-F#-G-A in this implementation emphasizes the V degree and the *Hijaz* tetrachord B-C-D#-E. [[See Supplementary Audio-21](#)]

However, the tuning practices amongst musicians are not any different in relation to the *Nakriz* music than they are for the *Hijaz* music: the tones of the augmented 2nd are often contracted or shrunken, emphasizing the chromatic shading that pushes the unstable tone towards the target anchor tone (Marcus 1993). Hemiolic similarity of *Nakriz* and *Hijaz* is evident from the fact that they both share basically the

same set of pitch classes (*Hijaz* that is built from D closely resembles *Nawa Athar* built from C), and therefore are often paired by a modulation (Manuel 1989a).

The position of the hemiolic gap in *Nakriz* is also enclosed *inside* the modal subset: the Eb does not bear the tonic function (unlike the Western C minor, which *Nakriz* might appear to resemble to a listener habituated to Western music). Moreover, whenever a *Nakriz* melody receives an accompaniment (usually limited to drones), the music usually displays stronger modal features in comparison to the possible use of chords in *Hijaz* (ibid).

Manuel underlines that the typical patterns of accompaniment in Mediterranean music do not necessarily borrow chords of Western music: musicians often combine non-triadic tones into a chord, which indicates that the performers lean not on their knowledge of chords but on the sound of chordal functions (similar to "tonic" and "dominant" of Western classical music). This is especially pronounced in dance music, where the musicians are supposed to spontaneously extend music to support the dance, which promotes experimentation by joining together riffs, drones, alternative melodies or passages in contrasting modes and/or tonics. As a result, the accompaniment becomes nearly as fluent and diverse as a melody – in sharp contrast to the rigid chordal accompaniment in Western homophony that is very common in Western music. Nevertheless, in all such cases, musicians base their choice of pitch classes for their accompaniment on the melodic features present in a solo melody. Maqam musicians follow nothing remotely resembling a tonal plan or a pre-existing familiar harmonic progression of Western tonality.

The last remaining theoretical issue is that although Mediterranean tonality seems to have inherited the tetrachordal design from the Ancient Greek chromatic system, the gravitational maps of tetrachords in both systems differ in regard to their treatment of the hemiolic gap (Katsanevaki 2011).

- The Ancient Greek gap separated *a stable tone from an unstable tone*: the upper tone was permanent in tuning, while the lower tone was changeable. Furthermore, overall, the gravity was directed downwards, promoting descending melodic motion toward the end of a melodic phrase, and thereby associating the high register with tension, whereas the low register with relaxation. Subsequently, the succession of high-to-low registers necessarily brought about the resolution of tension.
- The Mediterranean key gap, as a rule, separated *two unstable tones*. This difference between the Mediterranean hemiolic and Ancient Greek modal organization is evident from the acoustic measurements and morphological analysis of the recording in the *Thminoyo* mode of a Syriac chant (Nikolsky 2016b). That *Thminoyo* mode is tonicized in Bb and emphasizes the melodic gap Cb-D at the bottom of its ambitus, while featuring many chromatic inflections in the upper tetrachords – quite similar to the *Hijaz* genre.

Both tones of the gap in the *Hijaz* tetrachord (low II and high IV degrees) are unstable and execute the function of a "leading tone" (i.e., akin to sharpening the G to make it "lead" towards the upper A in A minor) towards the neighboring stable tones. Namely, the upper unstable tone of the augmented second becomes the ascending "tendency tone", while the lower unstable tone – the descending "tendency tone." Both unstable tones are characterized by the increased flexibility in tuning and strong reliance on the melodic context: thus, in ascending motion their pitch value tends to consistently vary from that of descending motion.

Overall, hemiolic mode seems to be capable of inducing more tension than the Ancient Greek chromatic mode: hemiolic tetrachord readily supports melodic motion in both directions across all melodic

typologies (including wavelike, skiplike, and zigzagging), and therefore is likely to prompt performers to engage expressive tuning to exaggerate melodic tension and relaxation.

22. Audio demonstration: Etude in *dorios harmonia* minor system in *enharmonion* genus. Reconstruction of the Classic Ancient Greek improvisation in the enharmonic Dorian mode by the Tabouris Ensemble. Relatively low tonal tension. [\[See Supplementary Audio-22\]](#)
23. Audio demonstration: Iakovos Protopsaltis - *Doxology in Barys Tetraphonos Mode*, chanted by Archon Protopsaltis Thrasylvoulos Stanitsas. Strong harmonic tension is evident in this Neo-Byzantine implementation of the chromatic/enharmonic subsets: Gb-A-Bb-Cb(C)-D(Db)-Eb-F-F#-G-A#, with 3 hemiolas (low Gb-A, mid Cb-D, and high G-A#) and a prominent pyknon (F-F#-G, constituting 3 discrete modal degrees). [\[See Supplementary Audio-23\]](#)

Subsequently, hemiolic tetrachordal organization features greater gravitational diversity, easily subordinating one stable tone to another, just as much as subordinating one unstable tone to another – and flexing the hierarchic relations depending on the melodic direction and intervallic style. Together with the possibility for modulation and alteration, hemiolic mode then constitutes a more dynamic scheme of tonal organization, in comparison to the Ancient Greek chromatic system that was designed as means of rationalizing and simplifying the capricious microtonal intonations of the older enharmonic modes – thereby inheriting the descending tendency of the enharmonic melodic motion (West 1981).

Melodic directionality of Ancient Greek, Mediterranean and Western keys

The descending tendency was apparent to Ancient Greeks, according to the treatise “Problems” by pseudo-Aristotle, where the problem No.33 poses the question: why do the descending melodies sound more harmonious than the ascending melodies? – and suggests the answer that the lower tones appear more noble and euphonic in comparison with the higher tones (Aristotle and Mayhew 2011).

This matter deserves a thorough quantitative study: modern computer technology allows to run statistical analysis of huge databases of folk melodies to estimate if the prevalent melodic direction for a given ethnic style is ascending or descending. My overall musical impression is that the Ancient Greek style can be characterized as *ataraxic*, while Arabic, Turkish and Persian styles all share *climactic* character, promoting large-scale “build-up” of melodic tension. Of course, this directionality remains only a tendency: in order to get up, the melodic line has to come down – it is impossible to keep moving in the same direction for the entirety of a music work. The climactic melodic type keeps climbing up as an *average* of all the melodic phrases and can be terminated by a few descending phrases that would therefore perceptually stand out. Such typology is often encountered in the genres of vocal music like *Mawwāl* and *Qawwāli*.

The fact that the Greek notation system followed the nomination scheme based on a downward alphabetic series leads to believe that the Greeks thought of their scales as descending (West 1992, 192).⁵ The descending design is also evident in their common practice of inferring chromatic and enharmonic genera from the diatonic genus *exclusively* by means of *lowering* the normative diatonic degrees. Helmholtz stresses out that it is the position of the smallest interval in a mode that designates the preferable melodic direction – which for the Ancient Greeks was pointing down (Helmholtz 1885, 286) due to the flattening rather than sharpening of the modal alterations.

The smallest interval acts like a “leading tone” by setting the direction for the resolution of tension (Roederer 2008, 184). Experimental research confirms Helmholtz’ conclusion, indicating that the “leading” directionality originates from the expressive tuning by the initiative of performers who, as a rule, increase the interval size of the first step in a directional melodic passage, and proportionally decrease the last step in ascending passages, while inverting this treatment in descending passages, thereby stressing melodic inertia (Delviniotis, Kouroupetroglou & Theodoridis 2008). The flattening default of the Ancient Greek music system was likely to set in place the descending inertia in the Greek tetrachords, thereby establishing what David Huron termed the “tendency tones” (Huron 2006, 160) as part of the pragmatics of recognizing specific modes by ear.

Following this logic, the possibility of placing the smallest interval at the top as well as at the bottom of the *Hijaz* tetrachord, further emphasized by means of expressive tuning that can compress a semitone at either side of a tetrachord (Marcus 1993), would indicate the affordance for both, ascending as well as descending directionality. However, from generative aspect in relation to the alternative maqam tetrachords, the *Hijaz* tetrachord is likely to favor the ascending direction, since its gap can be produced by sharpening its III degree (i.e. the *Kurd* tetrachord E-F-G-A modulating into the *Hijaz* E-F-G#-A).

The maqam *Kurd* forms another very common genre (named after this maqam) in the Arabic tradition – which is characterized by the *descending* melodic motion (Touma 1996, 36) – just like the Ancient Greek Dorian mode. It is interesting that the modulation from the *Kurd* (E-F-G-A) to the *Hijaz* tetrachord (E-F-G#-A) reverses the way in which the Ancient Greek Dorian tetrachord (E-F-G-A) received its chromatic shading by lowering its III degree (E-F-Gb-A). This modulation from the Dorian mode doubtfully emerged prior to the Hellenistic period: the Dorian mode was central for the Greek national identity (they considered themselves Dorians) and therefore was probably preserved from modifications. The practice of modulating from it could have emerged in the Sabaeen culture, foreign to Greeks, and passed on to the North-West Hijaz through the Sabaeen colonies (Nevo 2003, 68), earning a special name for the “sharpened” modification of a mode.

What is crucial here is that the Ancient Greek system favored only one, whereas the Mediterranean tonality easily affords both directions.

⁵ Stefan Hagel argues that West’s conclusion is not conclusive and provides references to the passages from Kleonides, Aristides, Alypius and Gaudentios, which use ascending enumeration for pitches (Hagel 2005, 299). He also points out that the alphabet does not start on the modally important note, but on C# (required only in enharmonic Dorian genus) and ends on a modally insignificant note as well. Although the descending alphabet in itself does not constitute the descending scale, nevertheless generality of the alphabet exceeds separate examples by music theorists and testifies to the commonality and convenience of mental representation of pitch in the descending order for the purpose of studying music, which was the primary implementation for Greek notation. It could be that while some theorists could conceive ascending scales, lay music-users considered descending direction more comfortable.

The puzzle of the hemiolic gap

However, it should be noted that the hemiolic modes can sound surprisingly close to the Ancient Greek chromatic music. Hemiolic typology does permit to shift the anchoring function from the lowest tone in the *Hijaz* tetrachord to the chromatic semitone underneath it – similar to the *Hijazkar* mode (D#-E-F-G#-A-B-C-D#). The resulting structure will strongly resemble the Ancient Greek chromatic Dorian mode.

24. Audio demonstration: *Lolazorume*, Tajikistan. This lyrical song features very consistent modal implementation of two hemiolas, each with its own tetrachordal organization: D#-E-F-G# / A#-B-C-D# - strongly resembling the Ancient Greek Dorian mode. [[See Supplementary Audio-24](#)]

On the other hand, the very first use of a hemiolic-style gap could have occurred *within the Ancient Greek tradition* as a form of variation in the traditional chromatic shading. The Berlin 6870 papyrus, dated by 156 AD, contains a fragment from the tragedy *Ajax*, which features a special modal scale with the sharpened VII degree, forming an augmented 2nd in relation to the degree below it (the “*Hijaz*”-like tetrachord C#-D-E#-F#) (Pohlmann and West 2001, 58–9).⁶ Stefan Hagel (in private correspondence) pointed out yet another occurrence of the *Hijaz*-type tetrachord in the surviving Ancient Greek compositions: in the Delphic Paean ascribed to Athenaeus (D-Eb-F#-G, generated by raising the F, although the latter is not engaged as a tetrachordal melodic unit - F# and D are mutually exclusive in the vocal phrases of this composition).⁷

Athena Katsanevaki lists a number of sources that testify that the missing part of book III of “The Harmonics” by Aristoxenus, in fact, explained the alternative possibilities for a pyknon to be positioned at the top of the tetrachord or to be split in two small intervals placed on both sides of the gap (Katsanevaki 2011).⁸ However, such structures, even if they happened to be employed in a melody, must have been an exception rather than the rule of *melopoeia* – although the gapped tetrachord of the Aristoxenian theory could have penetrated the folk music practice of the local ethnicities in the Balkan region and Turkey, and prompted experiments in shifting the hemiolic gap in relation to a specific tonal center.

Yevgenii Gertsman underlines that methodologically Byzantine musicology did not break with the Ancient Greek foundation: the music was still processed “atomistically,” in terms of the smallest element of an intervallic distance between two adjacent tones (Gertsman 1988, 66–72). Once diatonic and shaded intervallic typologies made a notch in Greek music theory and practice, there is no reason to believe that the enharmonic and chromatic genera suddenly ceased to exist: if it is plausible that sophistication of their learning could have motivated their avoidance by the self-indulgent rich Romans in their music-making, on the Near Eastern soil, from where Romans used to import slaves skillful in arts, the chromatic style had much greater chances to make an imprint on local traditions.

⁶ Although the *Ajax* tetrachord seems to feature the leading tone, the exact intervals in it are disputable: i.e. raising in pitch could involve just a quarter-tone.

⁷ However there remains a possibility that the entire tetrachord was engaged melodically in the part of the accompanying cithara, provided that the accompaniment to songs could have featured passages and extra tones added to the dubbing of the vocal part (Mathiesen 1999, 362).

⁸ Technically speaking, the notion of a tetrachord in Aristoxenian theory implied a melodic interval of the 4th of a particular intervallic shape that was reproduced a 5th or a 4th above (or below) the original tetrachord to make a scale – which differs from the notion of tetrachord in the music theory of maqam (this distinction is made according to the explanation by Stefan Hagel, in personal communication).

The earliest Christians were very tolerant in cultural matters, and whichever intervallic traits had made it into the local cultures were likely to sustain unless they violated the Christian ethos (ibid., p.67) that took after the strict rules advocated by Plato, exemplified in Plato's definition of the Dorian mode (Crickmore 2006). The anti-chromatic rhetoric materialized into the Church policy only in the 7th century AD (Meshscherina 2000, 79) – leaving enough time for the hemiolic typology to obtain solid ground in folk music. A glimpse into such music is provided by Christodoulos Halaris in his album "*Akritika*." *Akritika* was the paramilitary force formed out of militaristic ethnicities from Isauria, Pisidian mountains, and Gothograeci from Asia Minor, who were granted privileges by the Byzantine authorities in exchange for protecting the borders from Arabs.

25. Audio demonstration: "*A Border Guard was Building a Castle*," Cappadocian traditional song, arranged in the Byzantine style to represent the *Akritic* music of the 9th – 14th centuries AD. The song is based on a formula that alternates between hemiolic and diatonic modes: G-Ab-B-C-D-F and G-Ab-Bb-C-D-F. [[See Supplementary Audio-25](#)]

All things considered, it seems that there is less difference between the Mediterranean hemiolic and Ancient Greek chromatic music than between the Mediterranean and Western tonalities.

Modular design and inductive reasoning behind the Mediterranean theory of composition

Just as much as the Western key embeds a bulk of information on the intervals, chords, and their typical progressions and distribution between voices/parts, the Mediterranean key embeds a bulk of information on the tetrachords, trichords, and pentachords available for melodic development at different registral positions in the ambitus, different directions of melodic motion, different positions within a music form, and in different rhythmic patterns. Mediterranean music strongly relies on *modular* design, most clearly manifested in the compositional practices of maqam (Simms 2003, 11). The latter is distinguished from Western tonality by the substantially greater share of re-using pre-existing melodic material, both of micro-level of music form (common melodic intonations) and its macro-level (common turns for melodic phrase).

Compositional modularity is most evident in the genre of *nawbah* (suite), where motifs are often combined to form 3-, 4-, and 6-sided modules in symmetric designs that is strikingly close to the calligraphic diamonds or hexagons, so common in Arabo-Persian ornamental decorations in architectural interior design and book illustrations (al Faruqi 1985).

Western art of composition was never driven by principles of ornamental geometry. Western artists found inspiration in much more abstract and general implementation of geometry in the form of proportionality in axonometric projections, such as the "musical proportions" advocated by Alberti, which then were applied onto large-scale proportions of sections of music form, taking advantage of visual representation of the score on a cartella (Reynolds 1987). Or, the architectural proportions could have been taken as the base for the polyphonic arrangement of parts: e.g., Guillaume Dufay reproduced the proportions of the new Cathedral of Santa Maria del Fiore in a motet composed for its opening (1436) (Trachtenberg 2001). Compositions of that sort rely on the *deductive* reasoning ("top-down" logic), where the details of the composition are inferred from an abstract general pre-compositional premise.

- A composition of Western tonality is conceived from *general* to *particular* (with the help of notation that has been required for professional music-making at least from the 13th century), resulting in the music structure that is considered optimal and finite in its presentation of a chosen

subject, and expected to be faithfully *reproduced* by different performers – a music composition here stands like a “cover-song”.

- A composition of Mediterranean tonality is conceived according to inductive reasoning (“bottom-up” logic), from *particular* to *general* (through spontaneous improvisation that uses the bulk of pre-existing rhythms and motifs according to the set of quite rigid rules), resulting in the music structure that constitutes just one of possibilities of presenting a chosen subject, *not to be reproduced* by different performers – a music composition here stands as an idiosyncratic to its performer rather than a “cover-song”.

Yet another important difference is that Western tonal composition relies to a much greater extent on the configuration of micro-level melodic structures in order to produce a *novel* sounding macro-structure.

Demand for originality has had formative influence on Western concept of authorship and “invention” at least from the Renaissance times (Long 2003). Originality of musical themes has been a determinant factor in acknowledgement of Western composers from J. S. Bach onward (Simonton 1980). The entire course of the 16-20th century development of composition practices reveals progressive reduction of productivity in reverse proportion to increase in originality (Kozbelt 2008).

The emergence of the composer-centered “work-concept” as the primary means of aesthetic evaluation of Western art music (Talbot 2000) concurred with the emergence of tonal keys in the 18th century, and this was not a mere coincidence. A Western composer was expected to design a musical space according to the science of music in order to convince the listener in the reality of the musical emotions – this task at least partially resembled the occupation of an engineer and entitled the author with the right of ownership of his intellectual property. In 1739, Johann Mattheson explicitly expressed this view in his advices to a good Kapellmeister, where he justified borrowing of someone else’s material only if it was returned “with interest” - i.e., “one must so construct and develop imitations that they are prettier and better than the pieces from which they are derived” (Mattheson and Harriss 1981, 298).

Modularity of maqam and of Mediterranean composition simply do not provide sufficient means for a composer to invent anything “original” – exuberance of phrases and motifs available for elaboration makes the culture of music-making here somewhat “verbose”. This is in a way similar to how a very excited person says a lot more than necessary in order to make a point. Add here an old tradition of eloquence, so revered in Persian and Arabic literature, where generous quoting is regarded as a virtue, and one largely gets the flavor of Mediterranean method of composing music.

In this tradition, musical material is thought of as “utilitarian” – meant to be utilized by anyone who needs it. In fact, the verbose character of this culture is directly related to the microchromatic versatility of its musical modes: Sami Shumays testifies that he himself uses at least 12 tones between his lowest standard for tuning Eb and his highest standard for E, which he chooses depending on which mode is currently active in the melodic development (Shumays 2009). And what tells him which tuning is right is his memory of the melodic models for each of the modes.

Shumays compares melodic models with the glossary of words, remembered as the sound of correct pronunciation, and reports that in Egypt and Syria he has encountered many ordinary people who could sing hundreds of art songs in the “expressive microtuning” associated with the corresponding musical mode. Wide adoption of such modal erudition can be compared with the ubiquity of expertise in lyric poetry across former Persian, Arabic and Turkish territories, when a reader can easily come up with hundreds of quotes from his favorite poets.

What is "original" in this type of music-making is not the realization of a particular *design* of a virtual musical space, but the *style* of joining the compositional elements together – in essence, a personal interpretation of a known mode (or group of modes), along with its characteristic modules, presented in the "right" pitch, rhythm, and form (Nettl 1974). Then, in eyes of the indigenous listeners, reproduction of the same mode by the same musician would constitute the "same" composition even if the recorded scores of the performance would reveal substantial structural differences. However, objectively speaking, such creative reproduction should not be equated with the concept of the "fixed" musical composition, as it is officially defined by the copyright laws of all Western countries. From the legal viewpoint, Mediterranean composition is not "fixed" but improvised – very much like Western jazz music – and for the same reason as jazz, it is not entitled to copyright protection (Nikolsky 2018).

Much of this compositional difference between Western and Mediterranean tonalities originate in their gravitational differences. Unfortunately, it is hard at this point to define the exact discrepancies in their tonal organization because of their mutual influence on each other (Zannos 1990) and the historic proximity that obstructs our identification of their characteristic tonal traits (they both stay very much alive as of today). There are plenty of compositions of Western tonal music arranged to represent "Spanish," "Jewish," "Gypsy," or "Eastern" music, which quite closely reflect the modal characteristics of the Mediterranean tonality (see the Bizet's example in the beginning of this paper). On the other hand, any attempts to arrange Mediterranean music for a band are likely to involve some kind of Westernization of harmony. The "crossover" compositions considerably blur the distinction between what constitutes Western "classical music" tradition, and what – a "Mediterranean" core.

Nevertheless, as a whole, a couple of important observations can be made:

- The *trichordal alteration* scheme of the Western tonality promotes *triadic* vertical harmony and generates complex vertical hierarchy of stable and unstable tones – supporting the *duophonic* model of conception of music, prominent in Western compositional practices from the 15th century on, including the most complex forms of polyphony that were composed by coupling two parts at a time (Moll 2014). The duophonic methodology is most evident in homophonic textures, which are usually conceived as melodic voice versus bass, with some harmonic filling in-between (Hindemith 1942, 113).
- The *tetrachordal alteration* scheme of the Mediterranean tonality promotes *modular* melodic organization and generates complex horizontal harmony, while reducing vertical harmony to the bare minimum – supporting strictly monophonic model of conception of music, whose arrangement in the ensemble setting remains virtually unchanged since the times of Antiquity. It is based on heterophonic principles and, at its most complex implementation, affords the simplest polyphonic devices, such as a drone pedal in the bass or a melodic dubbing (these devices were explored by Western composers prior to the 12th century and updated in favor of more sophisticated typologies of texture).

Hierarchical organization of Western vs. Mediterranean keys

The outcome of vertical hierarchic interactions is that both, tension and relaxation, can form different gravitational schemes when they are placed at different layers of texture. For example, the tones in a chord can execute different functions: a root tone usually carries a harmonic function, the top tone usually carries a melodic function and requires some emphasis from a performer, whereas the middle tones act as mere fillers, and should not be marked out at all.

26. Audio demonstration: Brahms - *Piano Quartet* in C minor, opus 60, second movement, Scherzo. Visualization by Stephen Malinowski demonstrates the distribution of the stable and unstable tones across the texture by means of harmonic coloring: using the color wheel to represent the circle of 5^{ths} (blue-to-orange representing tonic-to-VII, and yellow-to-green to represent the chromatic alterations). The listener has to continuously renegotiate the stability and instability values for all the voices and parts of a rather complex texture. [\[See Supplementary Video-26\]](#)

Cultivation of such frame of reference requires the skill to simultaneously process parallel streams of information, where a single tone could receive different gravitational values in different textural layers.⁹ Theoretically, consistent exercising of texture-sensitive gravitational differentiation is likely to promote the ability to quickly estimate the arrangement of multiple objects from a particular angle, and facilitate such operations as axonometric projections (see Nikolsky 2016a for the discussion).

Processing of Mediterranean tonality does not cultivate such a capacity. Instead, it cultivates the erudition of melodic intonations, motifs, and phrases, as well as the knowledge of basic modal units for melodic and rhythmic construction of music. In this scheme of perception of music, attention focuses primarily on the horizontal aspect of organization, assigning the cognitive resources of the listener to span over longer durations of music form: thus, in Persian *dastgah* the relationship of the components in a *gusheh* (a section of a *dastgah* with its specific theme and ambitus) often resembles the relationship between the *gushehs* in the entire composition (Nettl 1974). Improvisation within the Mediterranean traditions can involve large building blocks as well as medium and small sizes. Producing and consuming this type of music is likely to develop a singular view, zooming into the longitudinal disclosure of melodic events.

There is experimental evidence of different strategies employed by Western and Arabic listeners in perception of tonal organization in the *taqsim* (modal instrumental improvisation) (Ayari and McAdams 2003). Western musically trained listeners, along with performers and musicologists, do not perceive the hierarchical melodic organization of *taqsim*, which can result in not hearing modulations and modal elaborations: in such cases listeners are aware of the presence of some kind of development of melodic microstructures, but are incapable of perceiving them independently. Arabic musically trained listeners generally succeed in detecting the melodic organization. They differ from Western listeners by focusing on the *evolution* of improvised ideas throughout the entire composition: grouping together the detected small modal images into lengthy sequences, and capturing the manner in which the large-scale musical ideas are presented in the *taqsim*. Ayari and McAdams identify five prevailing listening strategies:

- 1) discrimination of pitches, intervals, and ornaments based on their contribution to tension or stability;
- 2) seeking a coherent link between the tones to form syntactic sequences appropriate to each phase of the development in music form;
- 3) identification of microtuning that marks modal functionality of a tone in a modal cell, and relation of it to the microtuning in the previous cell;
- 4) reducing a set of similar units to identify the modal core and generative root, recognizing a particular color and general air of modal inflections in music;
- 5) tracking the dynamic profile of a phrase to establish coherence between musical phrases and distinguish the sequences that belong to the same mode but differ in modal detail.

⁹ The very same tone is likely to receive a greater gravitational value once it is placed in the bass of a musical texture, have a minimal value, if placed in the middle of a chord, and call for exaggeration of its stability or instability, if it constitutes a part of the melodic line.

Evidently, this approach is characterized by detection of larger-scale changes and identification of familiar modal structures and microstructures. Focusing on the longitudinal relations of motifs and intonations demands a combination of great attention to the tuning detail and great memorization skills.

Listening styles peculiar to Mediterranean tonality: *tarab*, *duende* and *hesychasm*

To answer such needs, a special listening style has been forged amongst connoisseurs of the Middle Eastern music. Gilbert Rouget describes it as the attentive and concentrated listening that aims to attain a kind of illumination of a divine contact – a sort of trance with heightened mental awareness (Rouget 1985, 270). This listening style is not limited to religious music alone (most explicit in Sufi music), but covers the Islamic music in general. The latter holds the spiritual aspect of music to be the most important and adopts the doctrine of ethos and the theoretical foundation from the Pythagorean roots, as established by al-Farabi, the translator of Pythagorean texts in Arabic and one of the main Arabo-Persian authorities on culture and music. According to him, music is a spiritual revelation (not necessarily religious) of cosmic energy, charged with some ethos, and therefore requiring a special treatment on the part of both, performers and listeners (Leaman 2004, 106).

The notion of *tarab* – something akin to ecstasy from being overwhelmed by a particular affect, evoked by an art object, usually aural – is central to the Islamic music culture, equally applying to secular and sacred music (Racy 2004, 12). *Tarab* relates to both, to a class of music designed to produce an affect and to the effect produced by such music – which turns *tarab* into “musical elation” – musical, since it is usually triggered by hearing a particular musical mode or by discovering an interaction of the melody with some metric pattern (p.136). *Tarab* can also be regarded as a bliss, achieved by intense mental fixation on a particular musical mode (p.134). The performers are supposed to deliberately try to generate this fixation in themselves and then pass it on to listeners, who can be affected to the extent of being possessed by a *tarab* of a particular tune for days to come (Shannon 2013).

Cultural transmission of *tarab* leaves no doubt that it is indeed a phenomenological reality in the practice of traditional Arabic music. The best confirmation for this is the concept of “*saltanah*” – the state of self-absorption: initiated when a musician captures the innate feeling of a musical mode in his improvisation and succeeds in communicating it to the audience (Racy 2004, 123). The latter is looking forward to hearing the presence of *saltanah* and lets musicians know once *saltanah* is detected. The state of *tarab* in the audience during listening is highly visible and audible to a performer (listeners keep jumping, clapping, dancing, moaning or sighing, and verbally exclaiming), and is supposed to direct performers in their choice of development in the improvised composition (Cosentino et al. 1987, 23).

Tarab, in fact, constitutes the aesthetic core that supports the stalk of Egyptian, Saudi, and Syrian musical traditions, advertently or inadvertently providing the point of reference for all the neighboring branches of the Mediterranean tonality. The stronger the *tarab* of a musical performance, the higher esteem for its performers. Absence of the *tarab* discredits the music. *Tarab* sets very direct criterion for music appreciation that can be easily utilized over different genres and types of music. As a peculiar type of aesthetic emotion, *tarab* can be remembered, reproduced, and mentalized by a person who is experiencing it. Communication of *tarab* through a musical “glossary” of folk melodic intonations and motifs becomes a simple and straightforward test in exercising the aesthetic judgment. This is in stark contrast to a very complex “science” of aesthetic judgment in the tradition of Western classical music that requires extensive training and good teachers (Scruton 1997).

Tarab provides a rather stable and long-living reference tool: it is supported by the tradition of Qur’anic chanting - as long as recitation of Qur’an remains the axis of international devotional practice of Islam,

there is no reason to expect any decline of the *Tarab* culture (Racy 2004, 224). By contrast, the advance of modern technology allows for wide distribution of *Tarab* music and popularization of records of the most expressive *Tarab* artists who are now deceased. Cultural globalization offers channels for any music, even the one that is not that popular in its local vicinities to win public acclaim in distant parts of the world via networks of festivals, clubs, TV, internet (Shannon 2003).

Through all of the available channels of modern distribution, *Tarab* music keeps winning international audiences and starts becoming a multi-cultural phenomenon. Thus, *Tarab* musicians cooperate with Jewish musicians in their album productions in Israel (Brinner 2009, 158). Jonathan Shannon reports that in Syrian city Aleppo, a renowned multicultural musical center of the Middle East, *tarab* plays an important role in Syrian "aesthetics of authenticity" that sets the cultural standard of being different from the West – what Syrians call "oriental spirit" (Shannon 2013). Products of other cultures are validated according to this standard: i.e. the Arabo-Andalusian music produced by the Spanish musicians is judged by the Syrian audiences in reference to the presence or absence of *tarab* in the auditioned performance to indicate whether the music belongs to "oriental" or Western domains (Shannon 2007).

Tarab is not alone in the coalition of Mediterranean musics. Spanish flamenco has forged something quite similar to *tarab* known as "*duende*" (soul). Great Spanish poet, Federico Garcia Lorca, who also is renowned for his collaboration with Manuel de Falla in the research of Andalusian folk music, saw *duende* as the principal aesthetic feature that distinguished Spanish *cante jondo* as the Iberian cultural archetype. Lorca cited an old maestro of guitar: "the *duende* is not in the throat, the *duende* climbs up inside you, from the soles of the feet," explaining that *duende* is "not a question of ability, but of true, living style, of blood, of the most ancient culture, of spontaneous creation" (Lorca 2002, 263). This "*duende*" is clearly in polar opposite to the classicistic norms of Western music appreciation that are supposed to be "dictated by the muse" – forming an alternative style, which in Christopher Maurer's words: "appeals to spontaneous understanding, with little, if any, conscious effort" (Lorca 2010, X).

In his lecture "The Historical and Artistic Importance of Primitive Andalusian Song known as *Cante Jondo*" (1922) Lorca considered chromatic irregular *siguiriya*, characterized by its dominant "Phrygian" key, to constitute the oldest *cante jondo* form, preceding flamenco. *Siguiriya* is believed to have originated from the Byzantine chant with the catalyst influence of Moorish and Jewish traditions, some time after the 8th century, ultimately shaped by the Gypsy contribution in the 15th century (Walters 2007). The notion of *duende* seems to come from the old-time flamenco authorities: thus, the legendary singer, Manuel Torre (1878 – 1933), from the Jerez school, regarded *duende* as "black sorrows" (*penas negras*) in a sense of intense personal musical emotion (Thompson 1985).

The historic paths of Western and Mediterranean tonalities diverge in promoting quite different philosophies:

- Vertical harmony in textural and harmonic organization of Western tonal composition, especially pronounced in implied chords and chordal progressions of the melodic line, cultivates tonal hierarchy that assigns different stability/instability values to the tones detected in a single slice of the musical texture – including different values assigned to the very same pitch class (e.g., as a voice in a chord and as a member of a melodic phrase) – which requires somewhat "pluralistic" outlook from the listener to perceive a single instance of a tone in a few possible "hypostacies" simultaneously. This method demands a high speed of auditory scene analysis;
- Horizontal harmony in primarily monodic organization of "Mediterranean tonal" composition cultivates tonal hierarchy that assigns only one stability/instability value at a time to every melodic tone, based on strict rules of modal organization and modal identity of the heard tone

(its pitch class in a musical mode). However, this value has to be renegotiated for every subsequent occurrence of a given pitch class, according to the repertory of modal intonations and motifs). This method engages a "monistic" outlook, imposing no need in instant segregation of audio streams, but placing heavy demands on memory and erudition.

If the Western listener is accustomed to quickly grasping many different pieces of information, which can be paradoxical to one another, requiring classification and analysis "on-the-fly", followed by metaphoric interpretation; the "Mediterranean" listener is accustomed to zooming into one stream of information and holding in memory a multitude of melodic details over very long spans, continuously relating detected melodic sequences to the known entries from his "musical glossary."

This difference in listening strategies corresponds to the difference in composition methods. Western composers design music to reflect multiple states at the same time – most obvious in polyphonic genres, but evident in homophonic textures as well (e.g., the Quartet "*Bella Figlia Dell'Amore*" from *Rigoletto* by Verdi, where each of the participants expresses his/her own emotional state and corresponding musical themes). Creators of "Mediterranean music" design music works of great melodic complexity that may involve intricate symmetric arrangement of motifs (al Faruqi 1985) and reach a gigantic size, where a single composition would last for more than six hours (Pacholczyk 1993).

Sizes like that are exceedingly rare for Western classical music, despite its obsession with complexity and originality, and strong competition between the composers (whether they are live or long dead). The longest composition is "As slow as possible" by John Cage, but it can hardly be regarded as anything but a gimmick (its "performance" is supposed to take over 600 years). The duration of absolute majority of most popular Western compositions falls within the range of 3-5 minutes – reflected in the current 3-minute standard of Western music industry adopted for a piece of popular music (vocal and instrumental).

Similar antithesis can be drawn between the aesthetic emotions cultivated by Western and Mediterranean music cultures:

- Western tonality promotes *emotional theater* in a manner of a movie: even in the miniature genres like song, it is common to represent the *mise-en-scène* of a particular emotional state, event, or situation, where the spectator observes them as though "from aside," aware of the theatric "fakeness."
- Mediterranean *tarab* places the spectator right in the same frame as the musicians who are supposed to generate aesthetic emotions – the spectator receives "the real thing," which is not realistic in a "mise-en-scène" sense, but its abstracted affectation engages the most direct emotional response on the part of the listener.

The Mediterranean listener takes musical things "for real" – and that could be the divider between the recent exacerbation of cultural conflict between the values of Western and Islamic lifestyles. Different cognitive schemes, embedded in Western tonality, could foster pluralism, and develop the ability to critically examine a situation from multiple angles before inferring an optimal approach to that situation.

On the other hand, the fixedness and directedness of the listening style cultivated by the Mediterranean tonality might be responsible for some of the mental traits that characterize the *tarab* culture: e.g., commitment to a single point of view, estimation of long streaks of information in relation to this sole aspect and unrestrained passionate reaction in which music-users become locked for a long period of time. Such traits might form a common ground for *tarab* of maqam (along with its derivatives, such as Turkish *makam* and Uzbek *shashmaqom*), *duende* of flamenco, and *hesychasm* of Orthodox plainchant.

Although *hesychasm* made its reputation as an ascetic instrument of diverting attention from senses to an inward seclusion to establish an experiential connection to God, its technique of focusing on nothing but the ultimate reality of God makes *hesychasm* essentially a feeling – a feeling that is supposed to replace all thoughts (Ware 2000, 102). Such a powerful feeling often takes shape of elation or ecstasy, quite similar to the experience of *tarab*. Orthodox authorities, like St. Maximus the Confessor, are explicit in that emotions and affections are not to be excluded from Christian worship for constituting an organic part of human nature, and that Christian prayer, in fact, "should be animated by *eros*, intense and fervent longing for the Divine, so that our worship becomes truly an expression of erotic ecstasy" (ibid., p.62). As we see, the listening style required by recitation of the Qur'an and by the Orthodox liturgy are not that far from each other.

St. Gregory Palamas, the chief theologian of *hesychasm*, taught that during prayer, our faculty of direct spiritual awareness exalts the flesh to "commune together with the soul in the Divine" (p.63). The music of the prayer was supposed to animate the words and fill them up with emotions to reach the state of "worship of the mind in the heart" (p.64). The *kalophonic chant* was designed to satisfy such need for mystic exploration into the mysteries of the Heavenly world (Stathis 2014, 56–70). Elaborated during the 12-13th centuries in Byzantium, it spread to the neighboring Orthodox churches. Even in Russia, where ecclesiastical music has always remained strictly diatonic, the *kalophonic chant* maintained the characteristic Byzantine trait of refined "intertwining" of the generously embellished melodic tropes, elaboration of which ran quite autonomously from lyrics, presenting a peculiar "intertwining" of the textual and melodic elements – displaying strong ornamental properties (Martynov 1994, 114).

Musical ornamentation here reflected the same tendencies as Balkan geometric ornamentation found in the architecture of Greek Orthodox churches and in the manuscript illuminations. The pronounced opposition of such geometric ornamentation to the "illusionism" (the tendency to replicate the visible reality as close as possible to the natural prototypes) of the Western art played an important part in the critique of the Catholic and Protestant cultures by Orthodox aestheticians who praised the abstract and the stylized method of representing the perceptual reality (Florensky 1996). For Orthodox theology, the roots of its anti-illusionistic stand can be traced back to the 8th and 9th centuries Byzantine Iconoclasm, inspired by the influence from Islam and Judaism (Brubaker and Haldon 2011, 264–272).

In this light, the affinity of Mediterranean tonality with hypermodal organization, evident in maqam/dastgah as well as in oktoechos/hexaechos, obtains some deep meaning. Hypermodal opposition to chromatic alteration can be seen as an attractive feature in constructing the melodic "scapes" on the foundation of monodic textures, securing the autonomy for each of the melodic modules within a corresponding "hypermodal" subset, while achieving the integration effect, required by the ethos of a specific mode. The priority of the task to illuminate this ethos at all times - without alterations and cancellations inherent to the "accidental" nature of Western chromaticism – could have promoted the transformation of the Ancient Greek chromatic system into the hemiolic system, regulated by the hypermodal principles, until the conventions of hemiolic chromaticism were forged.

It should be underlined that the cosmological doctrine of "music of the spheres" lost its ground in the West towards the end of the 18th century, but retained its stronghold in Islamic and, to a lesser extent, Eastern Orthodox musical theories. Eight principal modes of Byzantine *oktoechos* and all of its derivatives in modern Orthodox Churches (e.g., Greek, Bulgarian, Romanian, Georgian, Armenian) are integrated into an 8-week liturgical cycle, so that chants in the 1st mode are sung throughout the 1st week, chants in the 2nd mode – through the 2nd week, etc. – thereby, observing the calendar order. The West never adopted this arrangement – not even when its political authorities became set on the idea of borrowing the *oktoechos* system from Byzantine in the 9th century (Hiley 1990). And it is this calendar

connection that secures the ground under the doctrine of ethos, embodied in the "music of the spheres" (Nikolsky 2016d).

The adherence to the principles of musical ethos in modal organization, together with modularity and ornamentation of the large-scale motivic organization in a monodic texture that requires the trance-like emotionally charged listening, characterizes both domains: Muslim maqam/dastgah and Christian Eastern Orthodox plainchant. Their other common trait is found in the high esteem for verbosity. Just as maqam music requires extensive erudition in common "sayings" by different music masters in each of the known modes in order for a musician to come up with "good" music (Shumays 2009), *kalophonic* emancipation of melody opens a new period in history of Orthodox liturgical music – a period characterized by the spread of "musical lexicon" treatises, such as the "Chironomic singing exercises" by John Koukouzelis, that listed numerous modes, tropes, melodic figures, and provided their semantic descriptions, theoretic explanations and music illustrations (Martynov 1994, 60).

Modular music form, ornamental melic design, "verbose" style of expression and the love for rhetorical amplification, manifested musically in exaggerations of the expressive tuning along with long durations of music, altogether, support a manner of expression that is distinctly different from the Western classical music.

Conclusion

Hemiolic modes could have played a pivotal role in the rise of Mediterranean tonality – stressing its ideological and aesthetic antinomy to Western music. Their divergence becomes evident if one takes into consideration that the diatonic modes of both systems share much in common, and their greatest differences came about at a later point, as a result of historic development of the chromatic music.

Yet another important reason for salience of hemiolic interval typology could be its heightened ethos elevated to the state of elation and ecstasy. According to Racy, *Hijaz* has a reputation of one of the most important and most ecstatic modes in the Eastern maqamat: "a mode that enters into the makeup of all other modes" (Racy 2004, 108). Racy reports of the expert musicians who emphasize the critical importance of microtonal adjustments in the intervallic structure of the *Hijaz* mode for the *tarab* effect to take place: prohibitive (e.g., not to lower the II degree above the tonic excessively), as well as prescriptive (to flatten the III degree by one comma while sharpening the II degree by another comma).

Perhaps, the hemiolic intervallic typology is there to embody the historic transition from a one-point alteration to a two-point alteration, identified for the Greek region by Athena Katsanevaki (Katsanevaki 2011). Two-point adjustment of the gapped tones in a hemiolic "dominant key" could be exactly the binding agent in pairing the hemiolic "dominant" key with the diatonic "dominant" keys, so common in flamenco, in folk music of the Mediterranean region and in the Arabic, Persian, Turkish, and Gypsy art music. The "ordinary" (casual) levels of the emotional expression could be handled by the diatonic genus, whereas the extraordinary levels would prompt musicians to increase the size of the "alteration zone," thereby exponentially increasing tension and generating "augmented steps".

Note: The audio demonstrations originally linked in this paper (hosted on chirb.it, bit.ly, and loc.gov) are no longer available at their original URLs. They have been collected into supplementary audio files deposited alongside this paper on Zenodo. Each "[See Supplementary Audio File N]" reference in the text corresponds to the respective numbered file in the Zenodo deposit.

REFERENCES:

- Aarden, Bret J. 2003. "Dynamic Melodic Expectancy." Ohio State University.
- Ahrens, Christian. 1973. "Polyphony in Touloum Playing by the Pontic Greeks." *Yearbook of the International Folk Music Council* 5: 122. doi:10.2307/767498.
- Alekseyev, Eduard Y. (1986). *Musical intonation in the earliest forms of folklore. The aspect of pitch [Раннефольклорное интонирование: звуковысотный аспект]*. Moscow: Soviet Composer Available at: <http://eduard.alekseyev.org/rfi/index.html>.
- al Faruqi, Lois Ibsen. 1985. "The Suite in Islamic History and Culture." *The World of Music* 27 (3): 46–66.
- Aristotle, and Robert Mayhew. 2011. *Problems*. Vol. 1. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Atkinson, Charles M. 2008. *The Critical Nexus: Tone-System, Mode, and Notation in Early Medieval Music*. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press.
- Ayari, Mondher, and Stephen McAdams. 2003. "Aural Analysis of Arabic Improvised Instrumental Music (Taqsım)." *Music Perception* 21 (2): 159–216. doi:10.1525/mp.2003.21.2.159.
- Barker, Andrew. 2007. *The Science of Harmonics in Classical Greece*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
- Beaton, Roderick. 1980. "Modes and Roads: Factors of Change and Continuity in Greek Musical Tradition." *The Annual of the British School at Athens* 125: 1–11.
- Beliayev, Viktor M. 1990. "Modal systems in the traditional music of the USSR [Ладовые системы в музыке народов СССР]," in *Viktor Mikhailovich Beliayev [Виктор Михайлович Беляев]*, ed. I. Travkina (Moscow: Soviet Composer), 223–377.
- Bharucha, Jamshed J. 2002. "Neural Nets, Temporal Composites, and Tonality." In *Foundations of Cognitive Psychology: Core Readings*, edited by Daniel Levitin, 455–80. Cambridge MA: Bradford Books MIT Press.
- Blum, Stephen. 2002. "Hearing the Music of the Middle East." *The Garland Encyclopedia of World Music*. USA: Garland.
- Bowling, Daniel L., and Purves, Dale. 2015. A biological rationale for musical consonance. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 112, 11155–11160. doi:10.1073/pnas.1505768112.
- Bower, Calvin M. 2002. "The Transmission of Ancient Music Theory into the Middle Ages." In *The Cambridge History of Western Music Theory*, edited by Thomas Christensen, 136–67. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
- Bozkurt, Barış, Ozan Yarman, M. Kemal Karaosmanoğlu, and Can Akkoç. 2009. "Weighing Diverse Theoretical Models on Turkish Maqam Music Against Pitch Measurements: A Comparison of Peaks Automatically Derived from Frequency Histograms with Proposed Scale Tones." *Journal of New Music Research* 38 (1): 45–70. doi:10.1080/09298210903147673.
- Brinner, Benjamin. 2009. *Playing across a Divide: Israeli-Palestinian Musical Encounters*. Oxford University Press. <https://books.google.com/books?id=A2MIJa193Z4C>.
- Brothers, Thomas David. 1997. *Chromatic Beauty in the Late Medieval Chanson: An Interpretation of Manuscript Accidentals*.
- Brubaker, Leslie, and John Haldon. 2011. *Byzantium in the Iconoclast Era, C. 680-850: A History*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
- Chrisomalis, Stephen. 2010. *Numerical Notation: A Comparative History*. Cambridge University Press.
- Chrysanthos, and Kaitē Rōmanou. 1973. *Great Theory of Music by Chrysanthos of Madytos*. Translated by Kaitē Rōmanou. Bloomington, IN: Indiana University.
- Cohen, Dalia, and Ruth Katz. 2006. *Palestinian Arab Music: A Maqam Tradition in Practice*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.
- Combe, Pierre. 2008. *The Restoration of Gregorian Chant: Solesmes and the Vatican Edition*. Translated by

- Theodore Marier and W. Skinner. Washington DC: Catholic University of America Press.
- Cosentino, Donald, John Kennedy, Douglass Price-Williams, Jihad Racy, and Johannes Wilbert. 1987. "Trance, Music and Music/trance Relations: A Symposium, UCLA, June 3, 1987." *Pacific Review of Ethnomusicology* 4: 1–38.
- Cosgrove, Charles H. 2006. "Clement of Alexandria and Early Christian Music." *Journal of Early Christian Studies* 14 (3): 255–82. doi:10.1353/earl.2006.0049.
- Crickmore, Leon. 2006. The musicality of Plato. *Hermathena* 180, 19–43.
- Csapo, Eric G. 2004. "The politics of the new music," in *Music and the Muses: The Culture of "mousikē" in the Classical Athenian City*, eds. P. Murray and P. Wilson (Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press), 207–248.
- Cuddy, Lola L. 1997. "Tonal Relations." In *Perception and Cognition of Music*, edited by Irène Deliège and John A. Sloboda, 330–52. Hove, UK: Psychology Press.
- Dahlhaus, Carl. 2014. *Studies on the Origin of Harmonic Tonality*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.
- Delviniotis, Dimitrios S., Georgios Kouroupetroglou, and Sergios Theodoridis. 2008. "Acoustic Analysis of Musical Intervals in Modern Byzantine Chant Scales." *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* 124 (4): EL262–69. doi:10.1121/1.2968299.
- Engel, Joel. 1904. "Jewish Music [Еврейская музыка]." *Dictionery of Music*. Russia: P. Jurgenson.
- Everist, Mark. 2011. *The Cambridge Companion to Medieval Music*. Cambridge University Press Available at: <https://books.google.com/books?id=pzPzAgAAQBAJ>.
- Ewell, Philip A. 2012. "Rethinking Octatonicism: Views from Stravinsky's Homeland." *Music Theory Online* 18 (4).
- Farmer, Henry George. 1925. "The Influence of Music: From Arabic Sources." *Journal of the Royal Musical Association*.
- . 1929. *A History of Arabian Music to the XIIIth Century*. London: Luzac And Company.
- . 1930. "Greek Theorists of Music in Arabic Translation." *Isis*.
- . 1963. "The Oriental Impingement on European Music." *Islamic Studies* 2 (3): 337–42.
- Ferreira, Manuel Pedro Ramalho. 1997. "Music at Cluny: The Tradition of Gregorian Chant for the Proper of the Mass—Melodic Variants and Microtonal Nuances." Princeton University.
- Florensky, Pavel. 1996. *Iconostasis*. New York: St. Vladimir's Seminary Press.
- Gadjibekov, Uzeir. 1957. *The Foundations of Azerbaijanian Folk Music [Основы азербайджанской народной музыки]*. 2nd ed. Baku: Azmuzgiz [Азмугиз].
- Garofalo, Girolamo. 1995. "Traditional Rural Songs in Sicily." *Música Oral Del Sur: Revista Internacional*, no. 1: 65–89. <http://www.centrodedocumentacionmusicaldeandalucia.es/opencms/documentacion/revistas/articulos-mos/traditional-rural-songs-in-sicily.html>.
- . 2004. "Music and Identity of Albanians in Sicily: Liturgical Byzantine Chant and Devotional Musical Tradition." In *Manifold Identities: Studies on Music and Minorities*, edited by Ursula Hemetek, 271–88. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge Scholars Press. <https://books.google.com/books?id=awgJ2LtnU6oC>.
- Gertsman, Yevgenii. 1988. *Byzantine Musicology [Византийское музыкознание]*. Leningrad: Muzyra.
- Gurney, O. R., and Martin L. West. 1998. "Mesopotamian Tonal Systems: A Reply." *Iraq* 60 (1998): 223–27.
- Hagel, Stefan. 2005. "Is Nid Qabli Dorian? Tuning and Modality in Greek and Hurrian Music." *Baghdader Mitteilungen* 36: 287–348. <http://cat.inist.fr/?aModele=afficheN&cpsid=17961761>.
- . 2009. *Ancient Greek Music: A New Technical History*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Heckenlively, Lura. 1900. *The Fundamentals of Gregorian Chant*. Tournai, Belgium: Society of St. John Evangelist, Desclée & Co.
- Helmholtz, Hermann von. 1885. *On the Sensations of Tone as a Physiological Basis for the Theory of Music*. Translated by Alexander John Ellis. London: Longmans, Green and Co.

- Herlinger, Jan W. 2002. "Medieval Canonics." In *The Cambridge History of Western Music Theory*, 168–92. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
- Hermas, Tatian, Theophilus, Athenago, and Clement. 2007. *The Ante-Nicene Fathers: The Writings of the Fathers Down to A. D. 325*. Edited by Alexander Roberts. Vol. 2. New York: Cosimo, Inc.
- Hiley, David. 1990. "Plainchant Transfigured." In *Antiquity and the Middle Ages*, edited by James W. McKinnon, 120–42. London: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Hindemith, Paul. 1942. *The Craft of Musical Composition, Book I: Theoretical Part, 4th Edition*. Translated by A. Mendel. New York: Assoc. Music Publishers.
- Hobden, Fiona. 2013. *The Symposium in Ancient Greek Society and Thought*. Cambridge University Press.
- Homan, Frederic W. 1964. "Final and Internal Cadential Patterns in Gregorian Chant." *Journal of the American Musicological Society* 17 (1): 66–77. doi:10.2307/830030.
- Hornbostel, Erich M. von. 1975. *Opera Omnia*. Edited by Klaus P. Wachsmann, Dieter Christensen, and Hans-Peter Reinecke. Vol. 1. The Hague, Netherlands: Martinus Nijhoff.
- Huron, David. 2006. *Sweet Anticipation: Music and the Psychology of Expectation*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- Katsanevaki, Athena N. 2011. "Chromaticism: A Theoretical Construction or a Practical Transformation?" *Muzikologija: Casopis Muzikoloskog Instituta Srpske Akademije Nauka I Umetnosti* 11: 159–80. doi:10.2298/MUZ1111159K.
- Kholopov, Yurii. 1988. *Harmony: A theoretic course [Гармония: теоретический курс]*. Moscow: Muzyka [Музыка].
- . 2006. *Musical-Theoretic Systems [Музыкально-теоретические системы]*. Moscow: Kompozitor.
- Kilmer, Anne Draffkorn, and Steve Tinney. 1996. "Old Babylonian Music Instruction Texts." *Journal of Cuneiform Studies* 48: 49–56.
- Kluckert, Ehrenfried. 2004. "Gothic Architecture in Italy." In *The Art of Gothic: Architecture, Sculpture, Painting*, edited by Rolf Toman and Achim Bednorz, 242–51. Koln, Germany: Konemann.
- Koço, Eno. 2015. *A Journey of the Vocal Iso(n)*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge Scholars Publishing.
- Kowalzig, Barbara, and Wilson, Peter. 2013. *Dithyramb in Context*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Kozbelt, A. 2008. "Performance Time Productivity and Versatility Estimates for 102 Classical Composers." *Psychology of Music* 37 (1): 25–46. doi:10.1177/0305735608090846.
- Krumhansl, Carol L. 1979. "The Psychological Representation of Musical Pitch in a Tonal Context." *Cognitive Psychology* 11 (3): 346–74. doi:10.1016/0010-0285(79)90016-1.
- . 1990. *Cognitive Foundations of Musical Pitch*. New York: Oxford University Press. doi:10.1121/1.404005.
- Kutuzov, Boris P. 2008. *Russian Znamennyi Chant [Русское знаменное пение]*. Moscow: Andrei Rublev [Андрей Рублев].
- Kvitka, Kliment V. 1971. *Selected Works [Избранные труды]*. Edited by Goshovskii V. L. Vol. 1. Moscow: Sovetskii Kompozitor [Сов. композитор].
- Larson, Steve. 2012. *Musical Forces: Motion, Metaphor, and Meaning in Music*. Bloomington, IN: Indiana University Press.
- Larson, Steve, and Vanhandel, Leigh. 2005. Measuring Musical Forces. *Music Perception* 23, 119–136. doi:10.1525/mp.2005.23.2.119.
- Leaman, Oliver. 2004. *Islamic Aesthetics: An Introduction*. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press.
- Lester, Joel. 1977. "Major-Minor Concepts and Modal Theory in Germany: 1592-1680." *Journal of the American Musicological Society* 30 (2): 208–53.
- Lind, Tore Tvarnø. 2012. *The Past Is Always Present: The Revival of the Byzantine Musical Tradition at Mount Athos*. Lanham, MD: Scarecrow Press. <https://books.google.com/books?id=VPWjSeLibr4C>.
- Long, Pamela O. 2003. *Openness, Secrecy, Authorship: Technical Arts and the Culture of Knowledge from*

Antiquity to the Renaissance. Baltimore: JHU Press.

- Lorca, Federico G. 2002. "From Play and Theory of the Duende." In *Twentieth Century Theatre: A Sourcebook*, edited by Richard Drain, 263–65. London: Routledge.
- . 2010. *In Search of Duende*. New York: New Directions.
- Lundberg, Dan. 1997. "Welcome to Assyria: Your Land on the Cyber space—Music and the Internet in the Establishment of a Transnational Assyrian Identity." *Etnomusikologian Vuosikirja* 10: 13–28.
- Maniates, Maria R. 1993. "Nicola Vicentino's Reconstruction of the Ancient Greek Genera." *Revista de Musicologia* 16 (3): 16–36.
- Manuel, Peter. 1986. "Evolution and Structure in Flamenco Harmony." *Current Musicology* 42: 46–57.
- . 1989a. "Modal Harmony in Andalusian, Eastern European, and Turkish Syncretic Musics." *Yearbook for Traditional Music* 21: 70–94. doi:10.2307/767769.
- . 1989b. "Andalusian, Gypsy, and Class Identity in the Contemporary Flamenco Complex." *Ethnomusicology* 33 (1): 47. doi:10.2307/852169.
- Maraqten, Muhammad. 1993. "Wine Drinking and Wine Prohibition in Arabia before Islam." In *Proceedings of the 26th Seminar for Arabian Studies, Manchester on 21st - 23rd July 1992*, 95–115. Oxford UK: Archaeopress.
- Marcus, Scott. 1993. "The Interface between Theory and Practice: Intonation in Arab Music." *Asian Music* 24 (2): 39–58.
- Martynov, Vladimir I. 1994. *History of Liturgical Singing [История богослужебного пения]*. Moscow: Rio Fa.
- Mathiesen, Thomas J. 1999. *Apollo's Lyre: Greek Music and Music Theory in Antiquity and the Middle Ages*. Lincoln, NE: University of Nebraska Press.
- Mattheson, Johann, and Ernest Charles Harriss. 1981. *Johann Mattheson's Der Vollkommene Capellmeister: A Revised Translation with Critical Commentary*. Translated by Ernest Charles Harriss. Ann Arbor, Mich.: UMI Research Press.
- Mazel, Leo. 1952. *On melody [О мелодии]*. Moscow: Gos Muz Izdat [State Musical Publishing].
- Meshcherina, Yelena G. 2000. *Musical Culture of Russia during the Middle Ages [Музыкальная культура Средневековой Руси]*. Moscow: Znaniye [Знание].
- Meyer, Christian. 1996. *Mensura Monochordi: La Division Du Monochorde (IXe-XVe Siècles)*. Paris: Klincksieck.
- Moisil, Costin. 2011. "Romanian vs. Greek-Turkish-Persian-Arab: Imagining National Traits for Romanian Church Chant." *Muzikologija* 11: 118–32. doi:10.2298/MUZ1111119M.
- Moll, Kevin N. 2014. "Toward a Comprehensive View of Compositional Priorities in the Music of Dufay and His Contemporaries." In *Counterpoint and Compositional Process in the Time of Dufay: Perspectives from German Musicology*, edited by Kevin N. Moll, 3–63. Abingdon, Oxfordshire: Routledge.
- Nettl, Bruno. 1972. "Persian Popular Music in 1969." *Ethnomusicology* 16 (2): 218. doi:10.2307/849722.
- . 1974. "Thoughts on Improvisation: A Comparative Approach." *The Musical Quarterly* 60 (1): 1–19. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/741663>.
- Neubaer, E. 1992. "Music in the Islamic Environment." In *History of Civilizations of Central Asia*, edited by Clifford Edmund Bosworth and Asimov, 4:2:712. Motilal Banarsidass Publ.
- Nevo, Yehuda D. 2003. *Crossroads to Islam: The Origins of the Arab Religion and the Arab State*. Amherst, NY: Prometheus Books.
- Nikolsky, Aleksey. 2015. "Evolution of Tonal Organization in Music Mirrors Symbolic Representation of Perceptual Reality. Part-1: Prehistoric." *Frontiers in Psychology* 6 (1405). doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2015.01405>.
- . (2016a). Evolution of Tonal Organization in Music Optimizes Neural Mechanisms in Symbolic Encoding of Perceptual Reality. Part-2: Ancient to Seventeenth Century. *Frontiers in Psychology*.

doi:10.3389/fpsyg.2016.00211.

- . (2016b). Chromaticism in the modern hemiolic mode of the Syrian Orthodox chant: the heritage of the Ancient Greek music. doi: [10.6084/m9.figshare.13636166](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.13636166)
- . (2016c). Non-octave Hypermode as a special form of tonal organization of Orthodox Christian plainsong. doi: [10.6084/m9.figshare.14853657](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.14853657)
- . (2016d). Chromatic Alteration as Expression of Aesthetic Emotion: its Historic Roots in the Ancient Doctrine of Ethos. doi: [10.6084/m9.figshare.14872533](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.14872533)
- . (2018). *Possession Is Nine Tenths of the Law: The Story of Jazz and Intellectual Property*. San Francisco, CA: Academia [10.6084/m9.figshare.14852952](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.14852952)
- Pacholczyk, Józef. 1993. "Early Arab Suite in Spain: An Investigation of the Past Through the Contemporary Living Traditions." *Revista de Musicología* 16 (1): 358–66. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/20795894>.
- . 1996. "Music and Astronomy in the Muslim World." *Leonardo* 29 (2): 145–50.
- Pennanen, Risto. 2008. "Lost in Scales: Balkan Folk Music Research and the Ottoman Legacy." *Muzikologija*, no. 8: 127–47. doi:10.2298/MUZ0808127P.
- Petrović, Ankica. 1994. "The Eastern Roots of Ancient Yugoslav Music." In *Music \ Cultures in Contact: Convergences and Collisions*, edited by Margaret J. Kartomi and Stephen Blum, 13–20. Basel, Switzerland: Gordon and Breach Publishers.
- Picken, Laurence. 1953. "Instrumental Polyphonic Folk Music in Asia Minor." *Proceedings of the Royal Musical Association* 80 (1): 73–86. doi:10.1093/jrma/80.1.73.
- Pohlmann, Egert, and Martin L. West. 2001. *Documents of Ancient Greek Music: The Extant Melodies and Fragments*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Powers, Harold S., and Wiering, Frans. 2001. Mode. The term. Medieval modal theory. Modal theories and polyphonic music. *The New Grove Dictionary of Music and Musicians*. doi:10.1093/gmo/9781561592630.article.43718.
- Racy, A. J. 2004. *Making Music in the Arab World: The Culture and Artistry of Tarab*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
- Reynolds, Christopher. 1987. "Musical Evidence of Compositional Planning in the Renaissance: Josquin's 'Plus Nulz Regretz.'" *Journal of the American Musicological Society* 40 (1): 53–81. doi:10.1525/jams.1987.40.1.03a00030.
- Roederer, Juan G. 2008. *The Physics and Psychophysics of Music: An Introduction*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Science & Business Media.
- Rosenthal, Franz. 1966. "Two Graeco-Arabic Works on Music." *Proceedings of the American Philosophical Society* 26 (4): 268–73. doi:10.1016/S0016-0032(38)92229-X.
- Rouget, Gilbert. 1985. *Music and Trance: A Theory of the Relations Between Music and Possession*. University of Chicago Press. <https://books.google.com/books?id=NzT90FcmrI4C>.
- Sabaino, Daniele, and Marco Mangani. 2013. "Counterpoint and Modality in Gesualdo's Late Madrigals." *Philomusica on-Line*. <http://riviste.paviauniversitypress.it/index.php/phi/article/viewFile/1617/pdf>.
- Sachs, Curt. 1960. Primitive and medieval music: a parallel. *Journal of the American Musicological Society* 13, 43–49. Available at: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/830245> [Accessed December 10, 2014].
- Sanlucar, Manolo, Corey Whitehead, and Javier Alcantara-Rojas. 2011. "The Speculative Theories of Manolo Sanlucar: The Greek Origins of Flamenco Music." *International Journal of the Humanities* 9 (7): 7–19.
- Scruton, Roger. 1997. *The Aesthetics of Music*. New York: Clarendon Press.
- Scurtu, Bogdan, and C. Tutu. 2011. "Romanian Ochoechoi and Similarities to Middle Eastern Modes and Practices: A Case Study (part I)." *Scientific Bulletin of the Transylvania University of Brasov* 4 (53/2): 89–98.
- Shannon, Jonathan H. 2003. "Sultans of Spin: Syrian Sacred Music on the World Stage." *American Anthropologist* 105 (2): 266–77. doi:10.1525/aa.2003.105.2.266.

- . 2007. "Performing Al-Andalus, Remembering Al-Andalus: Mediterranean Soundings from Mashriq to Maghrib." *Journal of American Folklore* 120 (477): 308–34. doi:10.1353/jaf.2007.0060.
- . 2013. "Emotion, Performance, and Temporality in Arab Music: Reflections on Tarab." *Cultural Anthropology* 18 (1): 72–98. <http://www.culanth.org/articles/472-emotion-performance-and-temporality-in-arab>.
- Shestakov, Biacheslav. 1966. *From Ethos to Affect: History of Musical Aesthetics from Antiquity to the 18th Century* [Музыкальная эстетика западноевропейского средневековья и Возрождения]. Moscow: Muzyka [Музыка].
- Shulze, Bernhard F., and Ehrenhard Skiera. 1990. "Guitarra Flamenca." In *Flamenco: Gypsy Dance and Music from Andalusia*, edited by Claus Schreiner, translated by Mollie Peters, 121–46. Pompton Place, NJ: Amadeus Press.
- Shumays, Sami Abu. 2009. "The Fuzzy Boundaries of Intonation in Maqam: Cognitive and Linguistic Approaches." In *Conference of the Society for Ethnomusicology; 2009 Annual Meeting (54th): Mexico City, Mexico, November 19-22, 2009*, edited by Brenda M. Romero. Indianapolis: Indiana University Press. http://maqamlessons.com/analysis/media/FuzzyBoundaries_MaqamIntonation2009.pdf.
- Signell, Karl L. 1977. *Makam: Modal Practice in Turkish Art Music*. Da Capo Press, Incorporated.
- Simms, Rob. 2003. *The Repertoire of Iraqi Maqam*. Scarecrow Press.
- Simonton, Dean Keith. 1980. "Thematic Fame and Melodic Originality in Classical Music: A Multivariate Computer-Content analysis1." *Journal of Personality* 48 (2): 206–19. doi:10.1111/j.1467-6494.1980.tb00828.x.
- Smith, Nicholas, and Mark Schmuckler. 2004. "The Perception of Tonal Structure through the Differentiation and Organization of Pitches." *Journal of Experimental Psychology. Human Perception and Performance* 30 (2): 268–86. doi:10.1037/0096-1523.30.2.268.
- Sposobin, Igor V. 1969. *Lectures on the Course of Harmony* [Лекции по курсу гармонии]. Edited by Yurii Kholopov. Moscow: Muzyka.
- Stathis, Gregorius. 2014. *Introduction to Kalophony, the Byzantine Ars Nova*. Translated by Konstantinos Terzopoulos. Oxford: Peter Lang.
- Subirats, Maria-Angels. 2006. "The Special Role of Music in Judeo-Sephardic Culture." In *The Past in the Present: A Multidisciplinary Approach*, edited by Fabio Mugnaini, Pádraig Héalaí, and Tok Freeland Thompson, 107–18. editpress.
- Sultan, Nancy. 1988. "New Light on the Function of 'Borrowed Notes' in Ancient Greek Music: A Look at Islamic Parallels." *Journal of Musicology* 6 (3): 387–98. doi:10.1525/jm.1988.6.3.03a00050.
- Talbot, Michael. 2000. "The Work-Concept and Composer-Centredness." In *The Musical Work: Reality or Invention*, edited by Michael Talbot, 168–86. Liverpool, UK: Liverpool University Press.
- Thompson, Barbara. 1985. "Flamenco: A Tradition in Evolution." *The World of Music* 27 (3): 67–80.
- Tischler, Hans. 1973. "'Musica Ficta' in the Thirteenth Century." *Music & Letters* 54 (1): 38–56.
- . 1999. "On Modality in Trouvère Melodies." *Acta Musicologica* 71 (1): 76–81.
- Touma, Habib Hassan. 1996. *The Music of the Arabs*. Portland, Oregon: Amadeus Press.
- Trachtenberg, Marvin. 2001. "Architecture and Music Reunited: A New Reading of Dufay's 'Nuper Rosarum Flores' and the Cathedral of Florence." *Renaissance Quarterly* 54 (3): 740. doi:10.2307/1261923.
- Tsuzaki, Minoru. 1991. "Effects of the Preceding Scale on Melodic Interval Judgement in Terms of Equality and Size." *Music Perception* 9 (1): 47–70.
- Unruh, Patricia. 1983. "'Fumeur' Poetry and Music of the Chantilly Codex : A Study of Its Meaning and Background." Vancouver, Canada: University of British Columbia. doi:10.14288/1.0095778.
- Vuvan, Dominique T., and Mark A. Schmuckler. 2011. "Tonal Hierarchy Representations in Auditory Imagery." *Memory & Cognition* 39 (3): 477–90. doi:10.3758/s13421-010-0032-5.
- Walters, Gareth. 2007. "Music." In *A Companion to Federico García Lorca*, edited by Federico Bonaddio, 63–

83. Woodbridge, Suffolk, UK: Tamesis. <https://books.google.com/books?id=EQM3y6WmQoYC>.
- Ware, Kallistos. 2000. *The Inner Kingdom*. Crestwood, New York: St Vladimir's Seminary Press.
- West, Martin L. 1981. "The Singing of Homer and the Modes of Early Greek Music." *The Journal of Hellenic Studies* 101: 113–29. doi:10.2307/629848.
- . 1992. *Ancient Greek Music*. New York, London: Oxford University Press.
- Westrup, Jack Allan. 1954. "Medieval Song." In *New Oxford History of Music: Early Medieval Music up to 1300*, 2:220–69. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press.
- Yöre, Seyit. 2012. "Maqam in Music as a Concept, Scale and Phenomenon." *Journal of World of Turks* 4 (3): 267–86. EBSCO accessory # 84609213.
- Zannos, I. 1990. "Intonation in Theory and Practice of Greek and Turkish Music." *Yearbook for Traditional Music* 22 (1990): 42–59.
- Zemtsovsky, Izaly. 2012. "M. Gnesin on the Modal System of Jewish Music [М. Ф. Гнесин о системе ладов еврейской музыки]." *Scholarly Bulletin of the Moscow Conservatory* 4: 6–25.